

MICHELE SANVICO

THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

FOUR YEARS FROM *THE CHTHONIAN LEGEND*:
SIGNIFICANCE, IMPACT, ADDITIONS AND MISCELLANEOUS
(PERSONAL) CONSIDERATIONS¹

1. Eight centuries of mystery and then a breakthrough

Eight hundred years. To say the least. Most probably, much more than that. Throughout this abyssal span of time the enigma of the Sibillini Mountain Range has been living its secretive life beneath an elusive, unintelligible veil of coyness, inexplicability and disguise.

Then, almost unexpectedly, four years ago the veil suddenly fell.

¹ Released on August 9th 2024 on <https://www.researchgate.net/> and <https://www.academia.edu/>

On March, 25th 2020, Michele Sanvico's research paper *Sibillini Mountain Range, the Chthonian legend* was released after a long string of related, interconnected articles, and a bright light was finally shed upon a riddle that had been puzzling the minds of prominent men in Europe and the world for centuries and centuries.

An Apennine Sibyl's Cave and a Lake of Pontius Pilate, set amid the Apennines at the center of Italy. Two fascinating legends, two main characters - a legendary sibilline prophetess and a Roman prefect who existed in real life - two geographical landmarks that point to the spots from where the two legends elicited their remarkable, centuries-long power: a Cave and a Lake, lying just 5.2 miles from one another, within the same mountainous range, named "Sibillini" after one of the two legends.

In the past, a fatal attraction arising from the two legendary tales has drawn to this secluded portion of Italy European travellers of all sorts, including aristocratic knights, sorcerers, scholars, treasure hunters, poets and scientists, in search of a magical kingdom hidden beneath the cave's entryway situated on the top of Mount Sibyl, or looking for an appropriate site where to consecrate spellbooks to demons. Literary references about those visits span from the fourteenth century - with a mention of the lake reported by Petrus Berchorius - to the fifteenth century - with the fundamental works written by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale - up to our contemporary world, across the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries during which a bounty of references is found.

But why those legends rooted their peculiar fascination exactly here?

Since the very first mention we can retrieve, provided by Berchorius, nobody has been able to solve this perplexing riddle by proposing a viable reason for the birth (or the establishment) of such legends in this specific geographical spot.

The historical authors, from the Middle Ages to the Age of Enlightenment, were only able to note that both legends are to be considered as inexplicable, and even totally unrelated: the impossible task of retrieving an origin or source whatsoever for the two legendary tales, which additionally seemed to have no common relation, led many scholars to simply deny the chance that any credible grounds for the tales could ever be found, thus

degrading the whole matter to the babble of local populace and a discussion subject for simpletons lured to this place from every corner of Europe.

Modern scholarly studies, which started in the second half of the nineteenth century with Alfred von Reumont, Arturo Graf, Gaston Paris, Pio Rajna and others, were fated by the same doom of inexplicability: the undeniable appeal arising from the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate collided invariably with a sort of concrete wall which prevented any further investigation on the origin of the two mysterious stories. No mention of that specific Sibyl or the presence in the Apennines of that illustrious Roman prefect was to be found in classical and medieval literature before the fourteenth century. Total darkness accompanied all attempts to illuminate the past, and scholars could only conclude that the whole subject was most probably destined to remain in utter doubt.

Then, the paper *Sibillini Mountain Range, the Chthonian legend* came in, as the final element in a row of a number of preceding papers already published on the same topic. And eight hundred years of perplexity and a hundred fifty years of modern scholarly doubts were dispelled.

Because the key to the question was hidden in one word. And the word was 'earthquakes'.

For the first time ever, a correlation was established between the origin of the legendary complex which lives amid the Sibillini Mountain Range and the peculiar seismic character of that same mountainous region.

Because the tales about a Sibyl and a Roman prefect are not original. They come from elsewhere (the Matter of Britain for the Sibyl, the early-Christian apocryphal writings for Pilate), and set there on previously-existent geographical hotspots: a Cave and a Lake.

These hotspots originally hosted, possibly and conjecturally, an Iron-Age cult devoted to the worship of earthquakes and their chthonian demons.

But how this conjecture could be established? And why all this happened only in year 2020, following centuries of perplexed, ineffective handling of the whole matter?

MICHELE SANVICO

THE APENNINE SIBYL
A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

SIBILLINI MOUNTAIN RANGE, THE CHTHONIAN LEGEND¹

PART 1

1. Unveiling the true origin of the myth

Italy, the Apennines. The Sibillini Mountain Range, a portion of the long mountainous chain which extends across the entire peninsula. Mount Sibyl and a Cave on its mountaintop. Mount Vettore and a Lake nested in the great mountain's glacial cirque. Two legendary tales, the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate. Centuries and centuries of visits, literary narratives and explorations.

The time has come now to address the most important, most critical issue connected to the fastnesses of sheer rock which raise at the center of Italy.

¹ Released on March 25th 2020 on <https://www.researchgate.net/> and <https://www.academia.edu/>

Fig. 1 - The original research paper *The Apennine Sibyl, A Mystery and a Legend - The chthonian legend* was released on March, 25th 2020

The present article intends to be a follow-up of that breakthrough paper, proposing answers to the questions laid out above, highlighting some further, significant aspects of the 2020 research and describing a number of outcomes and implications arising from the publication of the research itself.

Miscellaneous considerations are also included, many of them marked by a more personal character, so as to save the memory of a years-long, exciting elaboration process.

2. Methodology and the scientific framework

2.1 Hundreds of years without an answer, here's why

2.1.1 The methodology issue

How did it come that a formal, explicit connection between earthquakes and the Sibillini Mountain Range's local legendary heritage was never stated before year 2020, although so many scholars have been deeply pondering, across numerous centuries, over the odd stories about a Sibyl's cave and a Pontius Pilate's lake set in central Italy?

All in all, the specific seismic behaviour of the Sibillini Mountain Range is not an unknown feature (with major earthquakes occurred in antiquity and then in 1328, 1703, 1730, 1859, 1979 and 2016), so that throughout the centuries one or more scholars might possibly have had the chance to establish a tentative connection between the two apparently dissimilar ideas: recursive, devastating quakes and the presence within the same territory of odd legendary tales.

Paradoxically enough, a large international scientific conference was even held in two sessions (Cascia 2019 and Le Mans 2021) in the very territory of the Apennine Sibyl: *Living with seismic phenomena in the Mediterranean and beyond between Antiquity and the Middle Ages* addressed those same topics, including the relationship between myths and earthquakes. The venue in Cascia, set a few miles from Norcia, in the central Apennines, was explicitly selected because that land - the land of the Apennine Sibyl, her myth and her link to tremblors - had been hit by the devastating earthquakes in 2016 and 2017. Yet, nobody amid the researchers thought, before during and after the conference, that the Sibyl could have been the queen of all guests there. Nobody, just like in previous decades and centuries, established any connection between the legendary traditions which lived amid the Sibillini Mountain Range and quakes.

Let's repeat it again: no single author or scholar ever raised the question or established such a connection. No one ever thought about it. No one was aware of the possibility. They just rested for centuries in their puzzlement.

Not even a prestigious scientific conference dedicated to those same topics in the very places of the myth proved of any help to figure out the riddle.

Why did this idea never come up to the mind of anyone?

The reasons are manifold. And they are all linked to crucial methodology issues.

Both ancient authors and modern researchers have failed in applying a correct methodological approach to the complex, multilayered, problematic question that the Sibillini Mountain Range's legendary tradition represents.

The right methodology was finally applied by the Author of the present article from year 2018 onwards, leading to the unprecedented results which were published under *The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend* paper series.

Let's see how wrong methods have misled researcher for centuries. And how correct methods proved bountiful in 2020.

2.1.2 'Treat them as one': the approach nobody pursued

The first basic error in the management of the legendary heritage which lives in the Sibillini Mountain Range is duplication: the legendary tales told about the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate have always been treated as two separate, independent narratives.

But they are not.

From Petrus Berchorius to Antoine de la Sale, from Flavio Biondo to Leandro Alberti, from the sixteenth to the seventeenth century, and then from the philologists of the nineteenth century to the researchers of the twentieth, all scholars have confronted with the mysterious Cave and Lake with a same incorrect approach: according to them, the two legends had nothing to do with each other, and reports about them were written in the form of a mere juxtaposition of the two tales, mentioned side by side with no internal connection.

For instance, among many others, in 1550 Leandro Alberti writes that «on the portion of this towering mountain facing eastward, it can be seen that most famous Lake of which tales are told about the conjuring of devils summoned by sorcerers», with a subsequent remark which says «nearby, namely in the said Apennine, lies the huge, frightful, ghastly hollow which was named after the Sibyl...». Two tales, no mutual relation.

This sort of interpretative error persists in much later times, if as far as 1903 the great French philologist Gaston Paris writes that «not far from there [from Mount Sibyl] there is also the 'lake of Pilate'. I am not going to discuss the tradition, established since longtime, which says that sorcerers came to consecrate their spellbooks in a small island set in the middle of the lake. Neither Pilate nor the necromancers have nothing to do with their neighbour the Sibyl. I will address only the latter...».

But unity is one of the key elements to solve the riddle. The Cave and the Lake must be treated as one single legendary heritage. Separating the Sibyl and Pilate just means that the common features marking the two legends get lost in the analysis, and the investigator is left alone with a perplexing unattested oracle and an out-of-context Roman prefect to concentrate on.

Fig. 2 - The Lake of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave in the Sibillini Mountain Range, Italy: a single legendary system which needs an integrated research approach

Now we know that the two figures are just mere semblances, they set their roots there from elsewhere coming from specific, extraneous legendary traditions: there is no point in focussing on them, if not to identify and remove their spurious legendary layers, which shield the underlying myth.

So mutual relation and final unity is the correct path to follow, while duplication is an error. A persisting error, up to year 2020.

2.1.3 The previously-missing 'philological' approach

Another methodological error is linked to a sort of 'blind', 'fideistic' approach, lacking any real insight. An insight which is to be rooted in sound philological grounds.

For hundreds of years literary authors and scholars - from Antoine de la Sale onwards - have been confronting with the elusive semblance of a Sibyl of the Apennines, wondering at the odd consideration that no ancient source ever mentioned such an oracle, neither in classical nor in medieval catalogues; and the same happened with reference to Pontius Pilate and the demons which allegedly lived under the lake's waters, a puzzling occurrence as no relationship could ever be retrieved between this portion of Italy and the renowned first-century prefect of Judaea, so that the demonic presence was seen by all researchers as a mere silly tale to be appreciated only by the most gullible travellers.

Nobody ever tried to dig under that utterly singular sibilline semblance, never attested before, and that extraneous Roman officer, the man who sentenced Jesus Christ to death in a far-away province of the empire. Nobody made any attempts at investigating the true provenance of those perplexing tales, instead taking blindly for granted that both narratives were born, somehow and at some time in history, exactly there, amid those same Sibillini mountains: a mere leap of faith, totally unproven and, in the end, easily rebutted.

In fact this was not true, and a simple analysis carried out on strict philological criteria could easily have revealed a fact that is manifestly blatant: when we stop thinking of the Apennine Sibyl and Pontius Pilate as

native tales, we begin to appreciate their evident extraneous, foreign origin. The two tales were born elsewhere and were subsequently transplanted right into the middle of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

From a philological point of view, retrieving the actual origin for the two tales was no hard task (and - among a plethora of scholars - only a young Luigi Paolucci, in 1947, had pointed out exactly the right direction that researchers should follow): the medieval lineage of the Sibyl's tale easily could be traced back across the many texts which are part of the Matter of Britain ('Sebile' is a companion and alter-ego of Morgan the Fay); furthermore, a similar lineage was to be plainly revealed for Pontius Pilate, with an extensive collection of early-Christian and High-Middle-Ages works illustrating the legends centered on the cursed destiny of the prefect's dead body.

So philology should have been a mandatory pillar supporting the road to truth; a pillar, instead, which was incredibly eluded by illustrious philologists (Gaston Paris, Pio Rajna, Fernand Desonay and others). For instance, Gaston Paris seems to have never highlighted the existing, conspicuous philological link which can be obviously established between the metal doors «slamming day and night without rest» described by Antoine de la Sale as an access point to the subterranean realm of the Apennine Sibyl and the similar access point that is present in the thirteenth-century epic poem *Huon of Bordeaux*, with its statues «made of bronze, each man holding a double scourge, all made of metal and terror-inspiring. They never stop striking and lashing to and from, throughout summer and winter»: an amazing miss, if we consider that those same bronze men with their scourges were portrayed in an illustrated page of Gaston Paris' edition of *Huon of Bordeaux* published in 1898.

Fig. 3 - A drawing from *Huon de Bourdeaux*, edited by Gaston Paris in 1898, which shows Huon running his way through the bronze statues wielding their whipping scourges

So philology was a first pillar. However there was another mandatory pillar too, of a kind that no philologist would have ever been able to address.

This further pillar was 'outside-the-box' thinking.

2.1.4 The 'think outside the box' approach that career scholars cannot follow

Philology is not enough, even though this illustrious discipline certainly leads the investigator towards the right course.

For once you have dismissed the foreign tales about a Sibyl and a Roman prefect, you are apparently left with nothing in your hands. What was there before the two extraneous narratives came? Philology provides no answer: no earlier works ever mention Mount Sibyl or the Lake of Pilate, so why did those geographical locations attract so powerful, famous narrative tales? And what was there before the settlement of the stories concerning the Apennine Sibyl and Pontius Pilate?

There the search grinds to a halt. Any investigation gets stuck. Hands are empty, and the mission seems to become quite impossible.

The only chance is to think 'outside the box'.

Creative thinking is needed to establish new unprecedented connections: a merger of ideas coming from different sources and domains into one single, revolutionary vision, providing a new framework in which the whole problematic, multilayered issue gets finally in gear and begins to assume a totally new, utterly fresh significance.

In the Sibillini Mountain Range, if you want to think outside the box you sure must consider earthquakes.

But thinking outside the box, and thinking about earthquakes, is no matter for philologists, who have developed their professional careers working for decades on the same objects (texts, manuscripts, etc.) and with the same methodologies (text analysis, text comparison, etc.), often concentrating their efforts on tiny textual details, a 'vertical' insight which almost hampers lateral, 'outside the box' vision.

In addition to that, those people never lived in the Sibillini Mountain Range and so never experienced the meaning and mythical mightness, at night, of the terrific shake - both physical and spiritual - induced by the sudden, godlike coming of seismic waves.

That's why no scholar - from Arturo Graf in the late nineteenth century onward - has never thought about earthquakes and their connection to the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

An interconnection figure was needed, one who came from different domains, with the ability to bridge the gap amid separated, incommunicating knowledge fields.

Fig. 4 - Creative thinking was needed to cope effectively with the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range

The Author of the present article was the right figure, at the right time: a physicist; a scientific researcher in his early years; a long experience in multinational corporates; a penchant for journalist-like investigations on public interest issues often uniformly treated by the media system; a fascination for the Earth and its geological might. And, last but not least, an actual foot in Norcia, the Italian town which is historically linked to the tale of the Apennine Sibyl, and which experienced a devastating earthquake in 2016.

All the wires were there. They just needed to be interconnected. And this is what actually happened between 2018 and 2020.

2.1.5 The 'Good Sibyl' false trail

In this paper I want to dedicate an additional space, though short, to the 'Good Sibyl' false trail, which I already mentioned in the *Sibillini Mountain Range, the Chthonian legend* paper.

Much time was wasted and the solution to the Sibillini Range's riddle delayed owing to the diffusion, at least among the general public, of the unfounded model of a 'Good Apennine Sibyl': a sort of positive, feminist, protective oracle depicted as a benign character in strong relation with the local communities of women, teaching arts and crafts to the villagers and promoting peace as a memory of ancestral gynocentric societies, ruled by women and opposed to war. A vision mainly promoted by the Italian writer, poet and activist Joyce Lussu.

This unfounded, baseless model tainted the overall scenario by leading the public sentiment to consider a 'good', positive sibilline legend as opposed to a 'bad', dark Pilate legend. Again, a rift between the two legends was delved, which enhanced duplicity and its accompanying load of errors.

Because there is no such thing as a 'good' Sibyl: the two legends are both dark and fearful and 'bad', as philology clearly shows. The reason for that is that both legends are probably rooted in a same appalling background, leaving no space for kindness, gentle women and nice artistic crafts: earthquakes are a ghastly phenomenon and as such they have nothing to do with all that.

2.2 Living with earthquakes in the Sibillini Mountain Range (once and today)

As we will see in a subsequent paragraph, the occurrence of a series of powerful earthquakes in the area of the Sibillini Mountain Range between 2016 and 2017 was a triggering event and an effective propeller for the design and development of the conjectural model on the origin of the sibilline legends.

Earthquakes amid those mountains in central Italy are a permanent, terrifying companion, not only in ancient ages (as we have already shown in *Sibillini Mountain Range, the Chthonian legend* paper) but also in present times.

The revised edition (2023) of the Seismic Classification Chart elaborated by the Department of Civil Protection of Italy effectively shows what we already set out in *The Chthonian legend* paper: the area in which the Sibillini Mountain Range lies is at the top of the seismic risk in Italy, standing out in the chart as a sort of red-alert island in the middle of territories that are less prone to earthquakes. A veritable hot-spot, in which large-magnitude seismic waves might suddenly and lethally propagate.

In recent years, contemporary men and women have experienced the most appalling aspects of a large quake unleashing its godly might on the land. In addition to the testimonies already reported in the *The Chthonian legend* paper, we quote here further narratives recounted by people who were on the Umbria or Marche side of the mountains on that doomed day, October 30th 2016, when a 6.5-magnitude earthquake hit the country at 07:40 AM.

A resident of Norcia remembers that «the preceding night the ground had been rumbling and grumbling for hours from beneath, as if in the abyssal depths a giant pot was boiling and boiling, preparing itself to explode; we were all in a sort of anguished expectation, we were sure that something terrible was about to happen, it was now our turn after the preceding quakes of August, 24th and October, 26th». Another resident, living in Montegallo, a small hamlet on the eastern side of the mountain range, said that «the town hall was swaying back and forth dangerously, that was a vision that remains totally unforgettable. Everybody thought it wouldn't hold and was about to collapse before our very eyes. [...] All of us knew what all that meant. The shake was so absolutely strong. [...] The noise from beneath was frightful. The ground lifted and sagged as if we were onboard a raft surfing across the ocean's waves. We held on to our car not to be thrown to the ground and with terrified screams our friends outcried their utter terror. [...] As the quake stopped the bellow from beneath ceased too».

Fig. 5 - Seismic Classification Chart elaborated by the Department of Civil Protection of Italy (March 2023)

The listed words were pronounced by contemporary resident living in the area of the Sibillini Mountain Range: people who know perfectly what an earthquake is and what originates this natural event.

Nonetheless, a common sentiment of fear and irrational thinking connects modern men to the ancient inhabitant of central Italy, if we consider that people, in 2016, expressed all their emotional feeling towards the indelibly eerie character of earthquakes, no matter how 'civilised' they are: «such fears are so deeply rooted in people's heart», explained the same resident of Norcia, «despite modern scientific awareness; a fear which is ancestral, primordial and uncontrollable, today just as in the prehistoric age [...] It is the reason for the development, among modern people, of naive explanatory theories, which overwhelm any rational thinking or scientific knowledge, with the desperate urge to 'appease' the earthquake. The same impulses come to the surface, which once hit the ancient inhabitant of the land. [...] Furthermore, a 'personification' process emerges even in our

present time: 'today HE is enraged', ' here HE comes again', 'today HE's taking HIS revenge upon us': with these words people unconsciously express ideas of guilt and discipline, favour winning and dire request of mercy».

This fear turns into something of almost tangible if you just pay a visit to the western side of Mount Vettore, the highest peak of the whole Sibillini Mountain Range.

There, the might of the earthquakes becomes visible and real, like a blow in your stomach.

Up there, at an altitude of more than 6500 feet, just beneath a huge rocky formation named 'Cliff of the Eagle', the 2016 earthquake sequence fractured the mountain for its whole length, creating a many-mile-long fault line: a white, polished, marble-like vertical surface, 6 feet high, grinded by the rocks themselves in a few seconds as they slid over the neighbouring stones, as we already described in *The Chthonian legend* paper in 2020, prior to actually visiting the spot.

Fig. 6 - The western side of Mount Vettore, with the Cliff of the Eagle on the right and the white stripe of the earthquake fault running across the versant

But - when we visited the place in person, one year later - the emotional effect on the mind and soul was utterly overwhelming: before your very eyes, the supernatural power of earthquakes was shining in the sun, cold and smooth under your hands, as if it had been carved by the titanic sword of a god.

Fig. 7 - The godlike effect of the 2016 earthquakes on the side of Mount Vettore

It is within this sort of psychological framework that we can set our new conjecture linking earthquakes to the generation and development of myths concerning the origin of earthquakes in antiquity: a sense of dread that inundate heart, soul and mind, both now and in ancient times. A sense of dread which necessitates the introduction of suitable narratives, with a view to confront with the chthonian monster and find ways to assuage its wrath.

2.3. The winds that point to earthquakes

One of the most interesting elements we found when designing our conjectural model is the presence, amid the legends which live in the Sibillini Mountain Range, of the supernatural winds that accompany the narratives concerning the Lake of Pilate and the Sibyl's Cave, especially when necromantic rituals are performed near the two geographical spots.

As we depicted in the *The Chthonian legend* paper, such winds are a significant mark which hints to the relevance of the seismic element: in the classical (Greek and Roman) culture, earthquakes were supposed to be generated by chthonian winds circulating in extended cavities which are concealed beneath the surface of the earth, as expressed in the works written by Aristotle, Titus Lucretius Carus, Lucius Annaeus Seneca and Pliny the Elder.

In this paragraph we want to highlight the fact that chthonian winds are present not only in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* and other works, but also in the other major literary narrative relating to the legendary heritage of the Sibillini Mountain Range, i.e. Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch*: an occurrence we failed to present in *The Chthonian legend* paper, so time has come now to fill the gap.

In the 1480 edition of the romance, Guerrino is told the following about the Sibyl's subterranean abode and the visit once paid to the place by a knight whose name was Lionel:

«[...] but he had not got in because from the entrance's mouth he said that a great wind was blowing, so fierce that the very stones of the mountain could not resist to it».

[In the original Italian text: «[...] ma non era intrato dentro perché de la boca de la intrata disse che usciva sì grande el vento che le pietre de la propria montagna non li poteva stare»].

So this underground wind, as strange and perplexing as ever (but not in the light of our conjecture), is also present in *Guerrino the Wretch*: a clear sign that earthquakes are to be taken in consideration, because there is no sense in mentioning a subterranean air current, apparently totally out of context, if not in connection with the well-known classical, prescientific theory about winds and quakes.

Fig. 8 - The chthonian winds as they appear in Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (Chapter CXXXIX in the edition printed in Venice in 1480)

Again, a question arises: why did nobody ever take into consideration the presence, in the literary heritage, of such winds, odd and bizarre as they are? Why were those wind completely overlooked, while scholars liked better to center their interest in the ghostly figures of a Sibyl or a Roman prefect? For what reasons this sort of 'smoking gun' did remain totally unaddressed until the publication of the *Sibillini Mountain Range, the Chthonian legend* paper?

The answers to this questions are already set in the previous paragraphs of the present article: a basical methodology issue has flawed for centuries the research approach to the two legends, treated separatedly and in the absence of an 'outside-the-box' thinking.

Yet those significant winds were blowing strong in the Sibillini Mountain Range's area not only from Antoine de la Sale's and Andrea da Barberino's works, but also from further literary sources well known to scholars.

Francesco Stabili, the Italian poet, philosopher and astrologist known as Cecco d'Ascoli, who was born in the second half of the thirteenth century not far from Mount Sibyl, openly embraces the classical vision about subterranean winds and earthquakes in his poem *L'Acerba*, written in 1327:

«Quivers the earths out of the constrained blows,
Air and water perform their malign motion [...]
The constrained winds, which cannot escape
from the ground, stirred by Saturn,
they make us feel the earthquakes [...]
But in the good season the shaking comes
and doesn't subside, until the hard ground
doesn't breaks open because of that might.
This not always occurs, for the wind,
agitated with anger down below,
his might may lose after blowing.
So the mountains and hills and chasms
are generated by the constrained winds
which blow under the ground powerful and mighty».

[In the original Italian text:
«Trema la terra per l'inclusi fiati,
L'aire e l'acqua lor moti perversi [...]
L'inclusi venti che non pon uscire
For de la terra, moti da Saturno,
Fano li terimoti a noi sentire [...]
Ma vien nel dolce tempo el gran tremore
Et non se cessa fin che le coretta
La dura terra per cotal valore.
Questo non sempre adviene ché dico vento,
Movendose cum ira li desotto,
La soa potentia perde poi che iuncto.
Sì che li monti li colli et li abissi
Sono formati da l'inclusi venti,
Che spiran soto terra duri e spissi.»]

Fig. 9 - Subterranean winds and earthquakes in Cecco d'Ascoli's *L'Acerba* (from the edition printed in Venezia, 1476), folia b6r-b6v

Thus, in the area of the Sibillini Mountain Range scholars and poets were fully aware of the pre-scientific conjecture which linked winds in the abysses to earthquakes, the latter often experienced by the local inhabitants, if we only remember that a very large quake hit this very same territory on December, 1st 1328, with the loss of thousands of lives, as we reported in *The Chthonian legend* paper.

Weird winds and storms also appear in the famous excerpt drawn from Felix Hemmerlin's *De Nobilitate et Rusticitate Dialogus*, written in 1444. In this passage, in which the Swiss cleric established his fundamental connection between Mount Sibyl in Italy and the German Venusberg, Hemmerlin reports that «about Mount Sibyl set near the town of Norcia and the castle of Montefortino [...] they say that a great outrage of hails, winds and storms plagues the area» [in the original Latin text: «Et dicit communiter mons Sibille coniunctus civitati Nursie et castello montifortino [...] grandinum ventorum et tempestatutum insultus nimium vicinis locis importunus»].

Again, winds are staged in connection with Mount Sibyl, another significant sign that earthquakes may actually play a role in the sibilline legends which inhabit this land, marked by a peculiar seismic behaviour.

Fig. 10 - Winds and tempest at Mount Sibyl as mentioned in Felix Hemmerlin's *De nobilitate et rusticitate dialogus et alia opuscula* (from the edition printed in Strasbourg, 1500), chapter XCIV

And, as a matter of fact, the classical wind-earthquakes model reaches out across history up to very recent times, which immediately precede the introduction of Alfred Wegener's theory on continental drift in the 1920s. For instance, we find the prescientific model still creeping in a work whose meaningful title is *Endogenic meteorology (La meteorologia endogena)*, written in 1879 by Michele Stefano de Rossi, an Italian geophysicist who greatly contributed to the study of earthquakes in the second half of the nineteenth century:

«A glance at those tables [earthquakes and barometric curves] is sufficient to see how each single atmospheric low pressure area is accompanied by an increase in earthquake's occurrence, and how the highs in the seismic activity exactly match the lowering of the pressure. [...] Another blatant observation, in the same sense, is that faint earthquakes often occur during the fast changing of atmospheric pressure, both when rising and when going down. And it is in this same order of ideas and utterly significant what more than once happened in Italy, i.e. of earthquakes which run after the central focus of low pressure during atmospheric storms. Many times I observed seismic sequences active for a certain time span in a certain spot, which with their peak leave that spot to unleash their endogenic pulse might in a neighbouring place where, on that day, a lower barometric pressure allowed an easier and readier expression, because less hindered by the weight of the air».

[In the original Italian text: «Basta uno sguardo sopra queste tavole [terremoti e curve barometriche ndr] per vedere come ciascuna depressione

atmosfera sia accompagnata da un aumento nei terremoti, e come i massimi sismici coincidano esattamente colle diminuzioni della pressione. [...] Un altro fatto parlante nel medesimo senso è il frequente avvenire i terremoti più sensibili all'occasione dei rapidi salti della pressione atmosferica sia nell'ascendere, sia nel discendere. Ed è in questo stesso ordine di fatti e vieppiù eloquente poi ciò che già più volte si è avverato in Italia, del correre cioè che fa il terremoto dietro il centro della depressione nelle burrasche atmosferiche. Più volte io ho constatato il fatto di periodi sismici localizzati da più o meno tempo, che col loro massimo sfuggono dalla sede prescelta per isfogarsi dove in quel dì di massima forza impulsiva endogena la minima pressione barometrica permetteva lo sfogo più facile e pronto, perché meno impedito dal peso dell'aria».]

Fig. 11 - Relationship between earthquakes and meteorological pressure in Michele Stefano de Rossi's *La meteorologia endogena* (Milano, 1879), p. 160 and 161

Even though de Rossi doesn't identify the origin of earthquakes in the action of improbable subterranean winds anymore, he still retains some aspects of this ancient belief by maintaining a faint but clear connection between events which happen in the rocks beneath the ground and up above in the air, with a persisting role still assigned to winds and storms.

So earthquakes and winds are linked by a close, though mythical, connection since antiquity, and up to nearly our present age. And it is no surprise to find a feeble echo of all that in the very words pronounced by

our contemporary fellow men and women who had the appalling chance to personally experience the October, 30 2016 earthquake in the area of the Sibillini Mountain Range. Incredible as it may seem, winds still appear in their descriptions, as if Aristotle's model was still in place and widely accepted to explain the weird, frightful, destructive occurrence concerning the propagation of seismic waves:

«We saw the neighbouring houses move and sway, and we thought they wouldn't hold to this further quake; however, luckily enough they resisted. I sensed a light wind made of warm air. I don't know whether it was due to the unrest, the tumult or a direct effect arising from the earthquake... This I have never been able to ascertain».

«When in Norcia sudden gusts of wind occur, people gets worried and fears they might bring about an earthquake, as if they were a grievous omen».

[In the original Italian text:

«Vedemmo le case vicine muoversi e ondeggiare e pensammo che non ce l'avrebbero fatta a reggere a questa ulteriore scossa ma, per fortuna, non fu così. Io percepìi un leggero vento di aria calda. Non so se fosse dovuto all'agitazione, all'adrenalina o se fosse una diretta conseguenza del terremoto... Non sono mai riuscito a comprenderlo».

«Quando a Norcia ci sono raffiche improvvisi di vento, la gente si preoccupa e pensa che possano portare il terremoto, che siano un annuncio infausto»].

Such winds come from far-away ages, when people harrowed by earthquakes made frantic attempts at finding explanations for the appalling motions of the ground, in a hope to track a hint that may help them anticipate and escape the might of the blows: a need they still have today, just as in a long-gone past.

2.4. More on the ultimate sacrifice

In *The chthonian legend* paper, we dedicated a paragraph to a portion of our conjecture marked by a most heinous character: the possibility, though remote, that in the Iron Age human sacrifices might have been carried out at the Sibyl's Cave and/or Pilate's Lake to appease the chthonian demons of earthquakes, as part of the ritual cults performed there during the worst paroxysmal manifestations of tremblors.

Of course this is but a speculation; yet we mentioned a few literary hints that seemed to point to this particular direction.

The first hint, specifically self-evident, is the famous excerpt which is retrieved in the *Reductorium Morale* by Petrus Berchorius (Pierre Bersuire), written in the fourteenth century:

«And about that lake the most horrifying thing is what follows: each year that town [Norcia] sends a single man, a living man, beyond the walls that encircle the lake, as an offering to the demons, who immediately and in full view tear apart and slaughter that man; and people say that if the town does not comply, the country would be razed by the storms».

A second hint can be retrieved in a work written by Pierre Crespet, also known as 'Crespetus', a French Celestinian monk (1543 - 1594). In his treatise *De la hayne de Satan et malins esprist contro l'homme*, published in Paris in 1590, he tells of the two necromancers who had visited Mount Sibyl and were subsequently put under arrest:

«For all the services they required, they obliged themselves to honour the Sibyls with the titles of Dames and Princesses, and to offer a soul to them every year, on the very same day of the consecration of their spellbooks, for all the time of their lives».

In the present paper, we want to add a further hint we culpably overlooked in *The chthonian legend*. It is another well-known passage drawn from Antoine de la Sale's *The paradise of queen Sibyl* and concerning the Lake of Pilate:

«Not much time has elapsed since two men were caught, one of them being a priest. The priest was brought to the said town of Norcia and there was martyred and burnt. The other was slaughtered into pieces and then thrown into the lake from the very people who had caught them both».

[In the original French text: «Navoit pas long temps quel y fut prins deux hommes dont lun estoit prestre ce prestre fut admene a la dicte cite de norce et la fut martire et ars. Lautre fut taille a pieces et puis boute dedens le lac par ceulz qui les avoient prins»].

Fig. 12 - The killing of supposed necromancers at the Lake of Pilate in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château (Musée Condé), Chantilly, France, folium 5r)

All the listed examples seem to suggest that human lives might have been taken and offered to the demonic inhabitants of the two hot-spots (the Sibyl for the Cave, the demons for the Lake). And the most ancient mention, the one by Berchorius - which perhaps retains a closer connection with the true, most antique myth hidden beneath the subsequent legendary layers concerning a Sibyl and Pontius Pilate - explicitly refers to the character of the sacrifices as attempts by the local population to shun the destruction of the neighbouring land, a potential reference to earthquakes.

Might it all represent a viable, consistent assumption? Or, is it just a mere, fanciful theory, with no grounds at all?

Certainly, in *The chthonian legend* paper we tried to reconstruct the probable psychological approach, the likely state of mind with which the

ancient inhabitants of the Sibillini Mountain Range may have faced the largest earthquakes occurring in their territory: utter terror, need for reassurance, hectic search for a contact with the subterranean monsters or demons, readiness to resort to any ritual practice in the desperate hope to stop the ground's frenzied motion.

Fig. 13 - Eleanor Betts' *The sacred landscape of Picenum 900-100 B.C.*, in *Inhabiting Symbols - Symbol and image in the ancient Mediterranean* (London, 2003), p. 106-107

The suggestions presented here are similar to other indications elaborated by archeologist Rust Whitehouse in her book *Underground Religion: Cult and Culture in Prehistoric Italy* (1992), and subsequently mentioned by Eleanor Betts (*The sacred landscape of Picenum 900-100 B.C.*, 2003) with reference to Grotta Sant'Angelo, a cave set near Civitella del Tronto, a hamlet set not far from the Sibillini Mountain Range: in it, «the excavation

of the Bronze Age levels uncovered twelve small holes within an elliptical hollow in the rock of the cave, each roughly circular, some containing human bones», in a possible scenario in which «heavily carbonised human remains from pits in the Neolithic level» may represent «human sacrifices or remains of cannibalistic feasts».

However this interpretation has been subsequently dismissed by later scholars, so we still do not have today any archeological evidence of ancient rituals carried out by the Picenes or the Sabines in the Iron Age involving the ritual sacrifice of human beings. This remains only a conjecture, as fascinating as it may be when fancied within the framework of the legendary tradition living amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, with their powerful earthquakes and the terror they certainly unleashed among the local populations.

2.5. Earthquakes, myths and the current scientific framework

In recent years the international research has become increasingly aware of the existing relationship between natural events, especially those of a catastrophic character, and the generation of myths in ancient cultures: an evolving approach that signals a fundamental evolution from both the 'psychological school' (which linked myth and human subconscious psychology, following the interpretative paths opened by Freud and Jung) and 'structuralism' (Lévi-Strauss' interpretation based on the unchanging structural patterns of human mind), which both fundamentally disregarded the specific events narrated in each myth. As opposed to this, now the actual contents of myths, possibly connected to real-world events, are put at the very center of the scientific investigation.

In 1973 it was geologist Dorothy B. Vitaliano, in her fundamental work *Legends of the Earth: Their Geologic Origins*, who coined the term 'Geomythology': «the study of the actual geologic origins of natural phenomena which were long explained in terms of myth or folklore», often «associated with earthquakes, great floods, natural fires, and volcanic eruptions, plagues, and other natural catastrophes». She positively opened the way for an exciting race across ancient history and traditional myths; a

race which is still ongoing, and that now counts, as a brand-new step, the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Fig. 14 - Dorothy B. Vitaliano's *Legends of the Earth - Their geologic origin*, Bloomington, 1973

Starting from the second half of the twentieth century, this race has been involving an increasing number of researchers active in various disciplines. As an interesting instance we mention the paper *Exploring the nature of myth and its role in science* (Masse, Barber, Piccardi and Barber, 2007), in which further steps were taken in the direction of geom mythology. In this article the authors intended to «provide a somewhat different conception of those myths whose roots appear to lie in the observation of natural phenomena and events, in particular geological events». In fact they note that «seemingly, rituals and cults were not directed so much upwards, to the celestial heavens, but rather downwards, to ‘Mother Earth’. [...] much attention would have been paid to geological phenomena, and in particular those more connected with the underworld, such as volcanoes and earthquakes».

So here comes geology, and geological catastrophic events, as the most effective triggers for myth generation. No more - or not only - human

psychology, no mere mind structures, and even less sun and moon and stars and heavenly phenomena. Instead, geomythology introduces a primary role for factual events unleashed from down below, like volcanic eruptions and mighty earthquakes. In this new research context, geomythology was definitely here to stay: «our focus here», they write in 2007, «is on myth in geology, or geomythology [...], which we define as ‘the study of the geological origin of myths and legends’». And «it will require the application of a number of geological, astronomical, and archaeological tools, as well as those from the cognitive sciences, history, and the humanities»: this is precisely the 'think outside the box' approach we have mentioned in a previous paragraph within the present paper.

Following this long race, geomythology has now rightfully entered the scientific arena. Today many published papers present studies, debates, analysis and conjectures; international research meetings are being held on this highly-promising area of investigation.

As we already described, in 2019 and 2021 two sessions of a same major conference were held in Cascia (in the central Italian region of Umbria) and Le Mans (France), with the title *Living with seismic phenomena in the Mediterranean and beyond between Antiquity and the Middle Ages* (proceedings edited by Compatangelo-Soussignan, Diosono, Le Blay - Oxford, 2022).

One of the two venues - Cascia, at the foot of the Sibillini Mountain Range, a few miles from Norcia and not far from Mount Sibyl - was not chosen at random: as we know, a large earthquake had struck that same region in 2016, and the promoters intended «to contribute to the protection of the architectural and cultural heritage in regions characterised by a high seismic risk and to promote a culture of risk management among populations taking into account the impact of destructive natural phenomena», in an area which had just been hit by powerful seismic waves.

Geomythology was one of the many topics addressed by the speakers, whose works were subsequently collected in Part I of the proceedings (*Interpreting and living with seismic phenomena in antiquity: myth, religion and science*).

A most interesting article was presented by Kevin Bouillot (*Earthquakes, divination and rationalities in ancient Greece: the Greek oracle as a way of understanding the seismic phenomenon*), who effectively expressed the connection between earthquakes, oracular sites and cults, according to a view we also independently applied in our *The chthonian legend* paper concerning the Apennine Sibyl:

«The oracular shrines were especially subject to enquiries following a quake, or in fear for the aftermath. This approach implies the credence, shared by the enquirers, that the gods were the originators of the seismic events; as such, they were considered capable of preventing, dismissing, assuaging the next earthquake, or at least of sparing the lives of those who adequately offered to them adequate prayers, sacrifices and rituals» [translated from the original text in French].

Fig. 15 - Proceedings of *Living with seismic phenomena in the Mediterranean and beyond between Antiquity and the Middle Ages*, Oxford, 2022

Fear for one's own life. Fear for the fate of one's family. Fear for the ruin of one's land. And the rise of a chthonian cult to appease the earthquake's demons. This is what we wrote in *The chthonian legend* paper. And here

Bouillot powerfully explains how rituals and cults contributed to the management and dispelling of fears in antiquity:

«Before the oracle is queried, for the ancient Greeks earthquakes are violent, deadly, sudden, unpredictable, inscrutable events and utterly out of reach for men as they belong to the realm of nature, as they are the result of the actions of the gods. But, after the oracular advice is rendered, that same quakes become understandable, as they get linked to a sentiment of wrath and/or to an act relating to a being who is certainly of divine nature, yet known and familiar. Now the seismic waves have entered the realm of something achievable by men: i.e. religion and cults tributed to the gods by those same men» [translated from the original text in French].

In this sense the oracle acts as a «cure for anguish», reports Bouillot: and we think that this remark can be fully applied to our conjecture on the Sibyl's Cave and Pilate's Lake as well.

As we also affirmed in our own articles on the Apennine Sibyl, Bouillot stresses the fact that «this psychological function attributed to the oracle may seem unimportant to the eyes of a contemporary historian, who are well aware of the tectonic plate theory [...] But it would mean we are forgetting that ancient Greeks had nothing like that. Apart from the higher layers of society who might have been acquainted with the 'seismic' theories proposed by Aristotle, Lucretius, Seneca and Pliny the Elder, the stricken population had only the gods to bestow a meaning on the catastrophe, and only the oracle to trace the appeasement of god's wrath, and check the divine will and future mercy» [translated from the original text in French].

Earthquakes, myth generation, psychological and social function of myths in ancient cultures. We see that current research is now focussing on such aspects of myths, and the results we specifically achieved on the legends of the Sibillini Mountain Range perfectly fit this general framework, presently being constructed by many scholars all around the world.

In the same Cascia / Le Mans conference, Loredana Lancini, with her article *Shaped by Fire: Memories of Volcanic Activity in Mythological Accounts*, explained the role of myths in traditional societies, by expressing concepts that easily apply to the Sibyl's Cave and Pilate's Lake as well:

«Myths have been among the tools used throughout history to preserve and transmit knowledge about dangerous geological phenomena, allowing ancient populations to conceptualize and somehow analyse catastrophic events».

Lancini reports a number of ancient Greek myths, each connected to a geologically-relevant place. Among them, the legend of the shrine at Paliké (in southern Sicily, where a mephitic lake once stood) seems to provide instances of mythopoetic processes which might also have been in place at Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl:

«Palikè, situated by an area featuring a peculiar geological profile, seems to us that it might be considered as an excellent case of study to address the geom mythology approach applied to a cult. [...] The place shows a dangerous nature. [...] The cult here is strongly dependent on the physical environment in which it is hosted [...] a divinatory practice that summons the divine and asks for its intervention, and that cannot develop itself but in a very special spot, an extraordinary one, where divinity manifests itself and its own might. Thus the lake of Palikè represents a 'locus inferus', a chthonian place: craters and deep hollows bring along the idea of a communication and a passageway to the subterranean world. It is a borderline area, a land of instability, a place which shuns normalisation, a bewitching, attractive spot: for there can be established a contact and mediation with the gods, and there the Otherworld turns into a real possibility» [translated from the original text in French].

A geom mythology place, a particular cult: «we repute that it's exactly the choice of the place», notes Lancini, «which determined, as a result, the ritual practices that were chosen so as to establish a communication with the deities. [...] A specific ritual is defined at that specific place which is not to be re-staged anywhere else and sets the fascination of the lake and cult in the long run»: because the distinctive mark of geo-cults is «a relation of close association of the cult with the specialness of the local geology».

As we can see, we are exactly in the same framework model for myth generation we have been addressing when publishing our conjecture on the Sibillini Mountain Range's legendary tradition: we stand by places which

are to be considered as 'hot spots (as we described them in our paper *Sibillini Mountain Range, a cave and lake to the Otherworld*), where the Otherworld opens its blood-curdling jaws to mortal beings, and through which living men are potentially able to communicate with legendary, supernatural entities; terrific cracks, which break up the continuity in our physical world and allow mortal men to enter forbidden, terrific realms.

Nonetheless, a manifest paradox is plain for all to see.

How did it come that nobody at that specialised conference - held at the foot of central Apennines specifically in the wake of a large earthquake - never considered the Sibyl of Norcia as a primary geomythological subject for research?

This observation is so apparently absurd, and so closely connected the same disregard we already spotted during the last 150 years, that we will dedicate to the matter a few remarks in the next paragraph.

2.6. The Apennine Sibyl forgotten by geomythologists (but fully recovered by 'The chthonian legend')

The years are 2019 and 2021. The topic is earthquakes in the ancient Mediterranean region. The attendees are the most illustrious academics whose studies are centered on history, myths and geology. Geomythology, with its myths arising from destructive geological events, is part of the conference's scope. The venue is Cascia, in the central Italian Apennines, expressly selected after a large earthquake had hit the region a few years earlier.

A perfectly-fit setting for the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range and the Apennine Sibyl. She should have been the queen of the conference - «top of the list, king of the hill, a number one», as sung by Frank Sinatra in *New York, New York*.

But she wasn't there.

The odd paradox is that the Sibyl of the Apennines - a primary character in geomythology, with her thrilling link to those very same earthquakes that recursively use to hit the central Apennines - was actually there, just 17 miles away: but at that time nobody at the conference 'saw' her. Nobody 'sensed' her mythopoetic potency. She was never mentioned by the attendees and never entered any of the conference sessions (*The chthonian legend* paper had just been released in 2020, but still with no significant reception at that time). Her time - together with her geomythological fellow Pontius Pilate - was still to come.

How did it happen that a major conference on geomythology held in Cascia just missed the chance to recognise the legendary tradition living in the Sibillini Mountain Range as a major - though possible, conjectural - example of a myth arising from the same earthquakes the conference itself was fully aware of?

The answer to this question is the same we already provided in previous paragraphs.

For centuries, and specially during the last one hundred fifty years, men of letters and scholars totally failed to identify any rationale for the birth, or establishment, of such legends in the Sibillini Mountains area. No one ever found out, if not cursorily, the Sibyl's lineage from the Matter of Britain, nor the relationship between the High Middle Age's narratives on Pontius Pilate and the demons at the Lake of Pilate. In addition to all that, nobody ever conjectured any connection between the Sibillini's legendary tradition and earthquakes.

This course of events just progressed, as plain as ever, into the *Living with seismic phenomena in the Mediterranean and beyond between Antiquity and the Middle Ages* conference.

Truth was before their very eyes; but they just didn't see it.

As a matter of fact, the Appenine Sibyl's and Pilate's legends, at a first glance, seem to be mere tales of medieval origin. Not Roman, nor Greek. As such, they have not been much considered by academics, as those narratives appear to be not so illustrious, nor antique.

But reality seems to be different, as the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range appears to be potentially rooted in very old Iron-Age myths on earthquakes: that is, we are in front of geomythology to its utmost expression, and even before the Greek and Roman civilizations.

Yet the conference failed on this specific point. And a non-professional researcher, the Author of the present article and *The chthonian legend* paper, succeeded in an area in which academy's results proved to be quite disappointing.

3. Sibilline legends, further mentions

Within *The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend* paper series, we presented a number of literary quotes from different works and centuries which provided a comprehensive view of the fame and diffusion gained by the legends of the Sibyl's Cave and the Lake of Pilate around Europe.

In the present paragraph we now want to introduce further references, not originally included in *The Apennine Sibyl* series' papers.

3.1 Pietro Ranzano and a late-fifteenth-century mention of the Apennine Sibyl and the Lake of Pilate

«On one of the peaks of the Apennine is set the hamlet of Mount St. Mary in Gaul, in which territory that huge and horrible hollow and cavern of the Sibyl is found, that is what the people know as the Sibyl's Cave».

[In the original Latin text: «In unius eorum iugis positum est oppidum nomine Mons Sanctae Mariae in Gallo, in cuius agro est ingens et horrendum illud antrum et caverna Sibyllae, id est quam vulgus vocat Cryptam Sibyllae»].

This is the opening of a long passage written in the final quarter of the fifteenth century by Pietro Ranzano, Bishop of Lucera, a Sicilian scholar and dominican friar, who wrote a large, extensive chronicle of historical

and geographical character, the *Annales omnium temporum* (*History of all times*): eight huge manuscripted volumes, of which seven are preserved today at the Municipal Library of Palermo.

In his work, a full book is dedicated to Italy (*Descriptio totius Italiae*), and it contains a thorough illustration of the legendary traditions which lived amid the Sibillini Mountain Range.

«... Sibyl's Cave, that is reputed to be the access through which simpletons and wicked men creep into secret places, inhabited by some unknown Sibyl. They say recesses exist in which she rules over large crowds of people. There preciously decorated houses are found, and spacious halls, ever-green grasslands, gardens of all kinds...».

[In the original Latin text: «...Cryptam Sibylla, quod sit via per quam stultos et impios multos perhibent petere secreta loca, quae inhabitat nescio quae Sibylla. Dominam eam aiunt loci esse quae numero imperitet populo. Esse illic domos exornatissimas, amplissima atria, prata semper virentia, hortos omnis generis...»].

So, between 1475 and 1493 (when the author passed away), Pietro Ranzano reports the rumours and popular credences which concerned the notorious Sibyl of the Apennines, by quoting a number of legendary, fairy-like features already mentioned by Andrea da Barberino in *Guerrino the Wretch* at the beginning of that same century, and also retracing the words written by Flavio Biondo, one of Ranzano's sources and inspiring literary models, in his *De Italia illustrata*, published in 1474.

Fig. 16 - The original edition of Pietro Ranzano's *Epitome rerum Hungarorum* (1489/90), preserved at the National Széchényi Library in Budapest (Hungary); a revised version of the same text was subsequently included by Ranzano in his *Annales omnium temporum*

But Ranzano, who was in Perugia as a student around 1445 and possibly had the chance there to hear about the Sibyl's and Pilate's legends firsthand, adds more information and annotations, considerably extending the significantly shorter excerpts written on the subject by Flavio Biondo. Yet his opinion on the sibilline legendary tradition is harsh and clear:

«This and many other fairy tales, very far from actual truth, are told by foolish and impious people as to the Sibyl's cave. I have stumbled upon many idle men, unaware of the path to real truth, who maintained they had reached the Sibyl through that hollow and seen all the things that I described above. To them I have never believed, nor I ever will, for all those I saw and heard lived a miserable life afterwards, and met an unhappiest death. How could I, a Christian theologian and philosopher, ever credit such lies?».

Pietro Ranzano also mentions the legend of the Lake of Pilate, but, again, he places no reliance in it:

«At a higher altitude, but in the territory of Norcia, there is a lake [...] It is known among the populace as the Lake of Norcia. As its waters often raise from the depths and are thrown in the air, water motions in various parts of

the lake ensue. But those who behold this, unaware of the reasons, say that the waters are stirred by the demons who inhabit the lake. [...] So this renown has attracted many people, devoted to magical arts, as far as to visit the mountain and lake and the agitated demons who stir the waters; and, utterly forgetting any godly fears, they try to deliver to the demons books, written with various symbols, to obtain their consecration. [...] After they had marked a circle on the ground and drawn the letters, after performing the sacred rituals and all the acts that were to be done, they saw nothing and heard nothing from the so eagerly summoned demons; nor the book to be consecrated, thrown into the lake, ever came back in the hands of the owner, despite they lingered there for three full days waiting for an outcome of any sort».

Ranzano concludes by assuming that «possibly the fame of those places is not so antique», noting that «otherwise the ancient authors would have mentioned them, especially those who told the tales concerning the cult of false gods. Just like the Oracle of Delphi, that in Cumae and many others have been cause for wonder - caves and rivers and springs and woods - those same places in Norcia would never have been overlooked».

We are at the end of the fifteenth century, and the might of the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range is still strong. Pietro Ranzano, a theologian and scholar from Southern Italy, cannot skip and overlook the two powerful legends. They both enjoy a widespread renown, even though the classical authors he knew so well had never provided any description of these magical Sibyl's Cave and Pilate's Cave.

3.2 Niccolò Peranzoni and his extensive description of the sibilline legends

Amid the mentions which we did not present in our previous papers, the following quote drawn from a work by Niccolò Peranzoni is certainly a most interesting reference.

At the beginning of the sixteenth century, Peranzoni - a learned scholar from Montecassiano, in the province of Marche - wrote his *De laudibus Piceni - Sive Marchiae Anconitanae Libellus*, a celebration of his native land, with a description of notable places and facts. The work has been

handed over to us thanks to a 1792 edition revised by another later scholar, Giuseppe Colucci, and included in his *Antiquities of Picene region* (*Antichità Picene*).

Sometime between 1510 and 1520, Niccolò Peranzoni was well aware of the legendary traditions which lived amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, and when confronting with the list of towns and villages that interspersed his homeland, on reaching Montemonaco («Mons Monacus», but also «Montem demoniacum» in his words) he could not skip neither the Sibyl nor Pilate, so devoting many pages to the two fascinating tales:

«The reason for this name lies with two different reasons. First, because of the notorius, amid the populace, Sibyl's Cave, which they say it is to be found not far from that hamlet on the crests of the Apennine. Second, because of the Lake of Pilate, whose renown has run across all the nations».

Fig. 17 - Niccolò Peranzoni's *De laudibus Piceni sive Marchiae Anconitanæ Libellus*, as edited by Giuseppe Colucci in his *Antichità picene* (Fermo, 1792), Tomo XXV

[In the original Latin text: «Idque praesertim duabus de causis. Primum propter Cavernam Sibyllae vulgo famigeratam, quae non longe ab ipso oppido in Appennini jugo esse fertur. Deinde propter Pilati lacum jam omnibus fere nationibus divulgatum»].

First, Peranzoni addresses the mysterious cave set on the top of Mount Sibyl:

«So it is believed by the old, foolish and gullible faith of the populace that the Cumaean Sibyl [...] once left her subterranean hollows and the secret places of Hades, so they narrate [...] and in our present days that same Sibyl is still concealing herself in those same mountains [...] and there she shall stay until she undergoes a future trial. This is the reason why many people, drawn here by a pointless mistake, are in search of that Sibyl's cave, and so they waste their time in disillusion, their crave frustrated: in addition to that, they are often stripped off of their valuables and even killed by the local inhabitants, be they shepherds or herdsmen - who are in charge of keeping the mountains under surveillance - sometimes they are punished and beaten, and dismissed after receiving a crude treatment».

[In the original Latin text: «Putat enim insanae credulaeque plebis inveterata fides Sibyllam Cumanam [...] per tartaros meatus perque loca silentia Ditis deduxisse fabulantur [...] in hodiernamque usque diem Sibyllam ipsam in montibus ipsis latitare [...] et inibi ad diem usque futuri iudicii mansuram esse. Hinc est ut multi vano errore allecti cavernam ipsam Sibyllae petant, ibiquo tempus omne delusi conterant, nec optatis unquam potiantur votis: Immo ab accolis multotiens ac opilionibus sive pecuariis, quibus custodiendi montis onus demandatum est, aut expoliantur, aut necantur, sive fustibus multati non absque gravi poena dimittantur»].

Fig. 18 - The Sibyl near Montemonaco as it appears in Niccolò Peranzoni's *De laudibus Piceni sive Marchiae Anconitanae Libellus*, as edited by Giuseppe Colucci in his *Antichità picene* (Fermo, 1792), Tomo XXV, p. 118

Definitely Peranzoni does not subscribe to the possibility that a Sibyl might have established her abode for real beneath the mountains which raise their peaks near Montemonaco, adding that «if something actually appears amid those mountains, we must reckon that this is nothing but fanciful and fiendish illusions» (in the original Latin text: «unde siquid in montibus ipsis apparet, nil aliud esse credere debemus quam fantasticas diabolicasque illusiones»), with a further interesting remark:

«Such caves, which here are not unfrequently found, are nothing else but retreats for alchemists, in which they, out of people's sight, melt metallic ore or forge coins, as they use to do today in many places; so strong is man's desire for gold. But they just waste their time and coal».

[In the original Latin text: «cavernas, quae ibi passim reperiuntur nil aliud fuisse, quam Alchimistarum latibula, in quibus, ne a plebe conspicerentur, aut ara conflagant, aut numismata adulterabant, ut hodie etiam pluribus fit in locis; tanta est mortalium auri potiundi cupiditas. Sed operam simul et carbones perdunt»].

And as to the Lake of Pilate, Peranzoni has no kinder words:

«When considering the Lake of Pilate, many people, urged by a useless miscalculation, from day to day come to this place from the farthest places of the world to gain spellbooks for themselves by carrying out a demonic consecration [...] They want to do it here among many other lakes for two main reasons: first, because this very lake is so secluded from any attendance of men, and this is a requirement of magical art. Second, because just on the lake's shore two circles made of stones are found, and stones are carved with symbols; and they say that the circles are necessary to perform the magical rituals, one was inscribed by poet Vergilius from Mantua, and the other by mathematician Cecco d'Ascoli».

[In the original Latin text: «Sed ad Pilati lacum repedandum est, ad quem multi vano etiam errore compulsi, ex remotis mundi partibus in dies accedunt, ut libros magicos consecrationibus daemonicis sibi ipsi vendicent [...] Quod autem Lacum ipsum Pilati ad id efficiendum prae caeteris requirant, duo sunt in causa: Primum est quod lacus ipse remotissimus est ab hominum frequentia, quod ars ipsa superstitiosa requirit. Deinde quod duo ibi circuli super lapides incisi juxta lacus marginem quibusdam characteribus monstrantur, quos ad artem magicam consequendam necessarios ajunt, eorumque alterum Virgilium Mantuanum poetam, alterum vero Cicchum Asculanum mathematicum effinxisse praedicant»].

Fig. 19 - The Lake of Pilate in Niccolò Peranzoni's *De laudibus Piceni sive Marchiae Anconitanae Libellus*, as edited by Giuseppe Colucci in his *Antichità picene* (Fermo, 1792), Tomo XXV, p. 120

Niccolò Peranzoni then mentions the legendary narrative concerning the praefect of Judaea, Pontius Pilate, whose final grave would be set in that Lake, as his corpse was thrown in the icy waters after transportation to the mountain-top on a chariot drawn by two bulls (a tale already narrated by Antoine de la Sale a century earlier in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*).

The whole excerpt is marked by a sense of thorough disbelief: these are just silly stories, narrated by the naive populace («indoctum vulgus»).

3.3 Abraham Ortelius, the first modern atlas and the Apennine Sibyl

When Abraham Ortelius had his *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum* printed in 1570, he marked a milestone in the field of geographical sciences, as it was the first veritable modern atlas in history.

Fig. 20 - Abraham Ortelius' *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum* (Antwerp, 1603)

In this illustrious framework, the Apennine Sibyl could not be missing: in the gorgeous edition dating to 1603, Mount Sibyl was there, its position located with accuracy within the map of the "Marcha Anconae", known as "Picenum" in antiquity. And that was not all: in a view to highlight the utmost importance of that mysterious Italian mountain, Ortelius also included a detailed caption, which provides an evidence of the fact that his imagination had been hit and seized by this most charming legend:

«In this place, looming over the mentioned territory, where the Apennine Mountain Range exceeds itself with the most elevated peaks, that ghastly Cavern is found whose name is Sibyl's (people calls it the "Sibyl's Cave") and the Elysium is supposed to be there. The populace also likes to believe that in this Cave of the Sibyl a large kingdom exists, full of magnificent, kingly palaces and enchanting gardens, and sensual maidens and every kind of delightful pleasures in great abundance. And all these things would be available to those who dare to get into that cavern (whose entranceway is visible to all). According to what is reported, after a full year of stay the visitors are free to leave the cave (if they wish so) and are so blessed by the Sibyl that when they come back to the outside world they live the remaining time of their life in utter blissfulness».

[In the original Latin text: «Apenninus mons hoc loco, ubi huic regioni imminent, editissimis iugis se ipsam superat, in quibus Antrum illud horribile est quod Sibyllae cognominant (Grotta de la Sibylla vulgo) atque Campos Elysios fingunt. Vulgus enim in hoc Antro Sibyllam quandam somniat, quae hic regnum amplum magnificis Regiisque palatiis plenum, hortis amoenissimis confitum, lascivientibusque puellis, et omnis generis deliciarum copia abundantem possideat. Atque haec omnia communicari cum iis qui eam per hoc antru (quod omnibus pateat) adeunt. Postquam vero per annum in eo permanserint, liberam egrediendi facultatem (si velint) eis a Sibylla largiri praedicat, atque ex eo ad nos reversis, felicissimo deinceps toto vitae tempore uti asserit»].

Fig. 21 - Mount Sibyl in Abraham Ortelius' *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum* (Antwerp, 1603), table following p.

A remarkable annotation is that Ortelius also includes a section which thoroughly addresses the German version of the legend, which is related to Mount Venus (Frau Venus Berg) and knight Tannhäuser (Danhauser or Daniel, as it is mentioned in Ortelius' caption):

«In our northern countries this Cave is known under the name of 'Vrouw Venus bergh', as if it were a mountain inhabited by Goddess Venus. To this place are referred the rhymed lines that once the populace used to sing about a certain Daniel (so he was called in the song), who, after having dwelled for one year within the cave, later deplored the life he had been living there; so he left his Venus and departed to Rome, seeking the Pope and willing to confess his sins».

[In the original Latin text: «Hoc Antrum nostratibus quoque innotuit, sub nomine 'Vrouw Venus bergh', quasi dicas, Dominae Veneris montem. Inde versus quidam rhythmi Teutonici vulgo cantantur de quodam parvo Daniele (sic enim cantio eum vocat) qui postquam toto in hoc antro anno mansisset, eius vitae tandem poenituit, eoque, hanc suam Venerem deferens, Romam proficiscitur, Pontificemque adit, et peccatum confitetur»].

Fig. 22 - The caption on Mount Sibyl in Abraham Ortelius' *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum* (Antwerp, 1603), p.

Ortelius' caption continues with the narrative of the famous Tannhäuser's episode concerning the blossoming of the papal's staff:

«The Pope, reputed that his sin was utterly unforgivable, took the withered, dry staff that by chance he had in his hand and, after having driven it into the ground, said that Daniel's sins would not be forgiven before his staff blossomed with roses. Daniel, when he heard this reply, in despair for the salvation of his own soul, left Rome in sadness, and for a second time (accompanied by two sons of his sister), returned to his Venus. But three days later the papal staff was actually seen in full blossom; and so they searched for Daniel everywhere across the whole land, but he never reappeared. People believe he ended his life within that cave. This is the tale told by this chant, which trustfully narrates of the imagined Sibyl, or Venus».

[In the original Latin text: «Pontifex hoc peccatum minime veniale credens, baculum quem forte effectum et aridum ad manus habebat, in terram defigens, sua illi peccata remissum iri dicit, quam primum hic baculus rosas ferret. Daniel ex hoc responso de sua salute desperans, maestus abivit, denuoque (duobus ex sorore nepotibus secum ductis) ad suam Venerem revertitur. Triduum vero post visus est baculus efflorescere: quaesitus ubique terrarum Daniel, sed nusquam apparuit. Creditur enim, eum reliquum suae vitae terminum in antro hoc finivisse. Hac huius cantilene historia, digna cuius fides huic sue Sibyllae, aut Veneri imaginatae, deferatur»].

But how could the Flemish geographer Ortelius know about the Sibyl? Who told him of Mount Sibyl and its incredibly fascinating legend, so that he could include such a detailed description in his *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum*?

We are proud to provide another significant contribution to the research on the Sibyl's legend by publishing - for the first time ever - the potential names of the persons who knew both the Sibyl's legend and Ortelius: the men who explained to a northern-European cartographer the secrets of the Apennine Sibyl.

Acting as contemporary detectives, let's try to probe into facts so as to provide an answer to this thrilling question.

First, let's consider Ortelius' map, which shows the exact position of Mount Sibyl.

Ortelius did not create his maps all by himself, he had local contributors established in all European countries. In particular, according to researchers, the “*Marcha Anconae olim Picenum*” map designed by Ortelius was taken by an earlier map made by Vincenzo Luchino, a map publisher based in Rome (a letter dated 1572 exists in which a Roman librarian, Giovanni Orlandi, recommended Luchino's map to the attention of Ortelius).

Fig. 23 - Vincenzo Luchino, *La Marca d'Ancona* (Roma, 1564)

Furthermore, as reported by Giorgio Mangani (a well-informed contemporary researcher), the info included by Ortelius in his maps was «mostly provided by extemporary local correspondents, enlisted from a milieu of men of letters, aristocrats and sometimes even people from military ranks, not always able to collect the geographical elements they were asked for with a reliable methodology; they were rarely men of science, more frequently they used to be engaged in different areas of studies».

A list of Ortelius' correspondents is presented in the initial sections of the *Theatrum*, including a biography of Ortelius written by Francis Sweert, an intimate of the illustrious scientist. Sweert says that Ortelius had many friends of great prominence and learning, «amicos coluit magni et nominis et eruditionis viros». The biographer continues by mentioning the names of the fellow-scholars residing in various European countries of that time. As for Italy, the list includes «Fulvium Ursinum, Franciscum Superantium & Ioannes Sambucum».

Fig. 24 - Correspondents from Italy according to Abraham Ortelius' *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum* (Antwerp, 1603), biographical notes by Francis Sweert

Domenico Francesco Superantio was a geographer who lived and worked in Italy's Veneto province. Ioannes Sambucus - whose real name was János Zsámboky - was a Slovak historian who lived and studied in Italy. Actually it seems they have nothing to do with the Apennine Sibyl and her legend.

So the possible source for Ortelius' information on the Apennine Sibyl was possibly Flavio Orsini. But which one exactly? Actually there are two of them, bearing the same name and active in the second half of the sixteenth century: the first was a most illustrious historian, archeologist, and one of the greatest collectors of antiquities of his time; the second was the bishop of Spolegium (and also of Norcia) from 1563 to 1581.

Certainly both of them could have written the famous caption on the Apennine Sibyl published by Ortelius: for sure they both knew everything about the legend. So further research will be needed to ascertain who actually told Ortelius of Mount Sibyl, irrevocably consigning this thrilling fairy tale to the wider European lore. Yet, this is a most promising track.

3.4 *The Sibyl in the Cosmographie Universelle by André Thevet*

The legends living in the Sibillini Mountain Range could not be missing in the *Cosmographie Universelle* edited in 1575 by André Thevet, a franciscan friar and traveller whose works, often controversial, were stuffed with the bizarre and the picturesque.

«Near the hamlet of Arquata the Apennines are so elevated that they surmount in height all the rest, in all directions; because of this this elevated mountain-top is called Mount Vettore: and not far from there lies the town of Norcia [...] Near Mount Vettore, on the eastern side, there is a Lake, where some say that enchantments are performed so easily that the less skillful will be able to see the demons, who will reply to any question the enquirer may pose to them. However, as for myself I cannot believe that at all, and I've always taken fun out of this sort of accounts. [...] It's there that the most elevated Apennine peaks appear, on one of them is a Castle known 'Of the Holy Mary in Gallo': And nearby you can find that frighful cave and hollow that is known as the Sibyl's Cave: in it people believe is the kingdom of that said Sibyl, similar to a kingdom of Fairies, and marked by the silly tales which are told about a Fairy of King Oberon. Despite all that, the entrance to the sibilline caver has been filled up, and guards stand by the Lake lest nobody misuses the place in search of the favours bestowed by Satan».

[In the original French text: «Pres d'Arquate l'Apennin est si hault, qu'il surmonte tout le reste de sa haulteur, en quelque lieu que ce soit; qui est cause que ceste sommité ainsi haulsee, est nommee Mont Veltore: Et pre de là est bastie la ville de Nursie [...] Pres Mont Veltore, du costé de l'Orient, est un Lac, où aucuns dient que se font les enchantemens si faciles, que le moins sçavant y verra les esprits, qui luy respondront de tout ce qu'il demandera. Mais quant à moy je n'en peux rien croire, ains me suis toujours mocqué de tels comptes. [...] Et c'est là qu'apparoissent les haults monts Apennins, sur l'un desquels est le Chasteau du mont nommé 'Di Sancto Maria in Gallo': Et pres de là est celle espouvantable Grotte et spelunque, que l'on nomme la Caverne de la Sibylle: où l'on faist le regne de ceste Sibylle, tout tel que celuy de Faerie, et approchant des folies qu'on a compté d'une Fee de ce Roy Oberon. Neanmoins a l'on estoupé le trou de

ladicte caverne Sibylline, et tient on gardes au Lac, à fin qu'aucun ne s'y aille abuser, et n'use du ministere de Satan»].

Fig. 25 - Sibylline legends in André Thevet's *Cosmographie Universelle* (Paris, 1575), p. 759

It is a description which reflects information drawn from Antoine de la Sale and other geographical works; however it provides a further confirmation of the interest and curiosity that this geographical area, set in the Italian Apennines between the provinces of Umbria and Marche, was still arousing amid a vast audience in the late sixteenth century.

3.5 The Apennine Sibyl and the British Isles

Not many scholars are aware of the fact that the renown of the Apennine Sibyl, in past centuries, has reached out as far as the British Isles. We are

proud to present this mark, previously unnoticed, left from this peculiar Italian legend on a northern-European land: Great Britain.

In 1586, the illustrious British historian William Camden published his fundamental work *Britannia*, an outstanding description of the geographical features of the British Isles. On presenting one of the few caves which exist in his own homecountry, a hollow set near the town of Wells ("Ochie-Hole, known today as the "Wookey Hole Caves"), he wrote the following words:

«From there eastward the Mendip Hills stretch across an extensive area, and were called Mine District from John Leland [...] as there was plenty of lead ore, and sheep had their grasslands. In these caves a vast hollow is found, in which once were wells and rivulets; they call it 'Ochye-hole' of which the inhabitants hereabouts have related as many idle stories, as the Italians have of their Sibyl's Cave in the Apennine Mountains».

[In the original Latin text: «Hinc ad Ortum Mendippi colles se longem lateque explicant, Minerarios vocat Lelandus [...] plumbi enim fodinis opulenti, et pascendis pecoribus apti. In his antrum est longo recessu, in quo putei quidam, et rivuli cernuntur, Ochye-Hole dicunt, de quo non minora somnia fingunt accolae, quam de suo Sybillae antro in Appennino, comminiscuntur Itali»].

Fig. 26 - The Apennine Sibyl in William Camden's *Britannia* (London, 1587), p. 125

As a matter of fact this mention represents a most significant sign of the mighty diffusion potential featured by the Italian legend about a Sibyl living amid the mountains in central Italy.

But how it was that Camden could get aware of the existence of an Apennine Sibyl in far-away Italy? The answer is clear to our eyes: the Italian sibilline legend had probably travelled through Flanders. It is known to scholars that William Camden wrote his work *Britannia* under the significant influence of Abraham Ortelius from Antwerp, the renowned Flemish cartographer and the author of the greatest geographical work of his century, the *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum*, which we already described in a previous paragraph.

Ortelius made use of various correspondents based in various countries, who co-operated with him in the drawing of the many national geographical maps: as to the British Isles, he had established a close relationship with the same William Camden. An assiduous exchange of letters was in place between the two scholars, in which they discussed learned topics like the antique names of the places of Roman Britain and other erudite issues.

Possibly it was Ortelius who told Camden the tale of the Apennine Sibyl. Ortelius, the man who had definitely marked the position of Mount Sibyl in his illustrious *Theatrum Orbis Terrarum*, within the map of the "Marcha Anconae olim Picenum", and was so utterly fascinated by the narrative about the Sibyl that he accompanied his map with a long descriptive text, half of which was fully dedicated to the fantastic legend of the Apennine Sibyl.

From Italy to Flanders, and from Flanders to the British Isles: a wondrous travel for a Sibyl who lived amid the Apennines in the central portion of the Italian peninsula.

3.6 The Apennine Sibyl in a 1643 guidebook for travellers: David Froelich

When David Froelich, a Slovak geographer, mathematician and traveller, published his *Bibliothecae Sive Cynosurae Peregrinantium, hoc est, Viatorii Liber* in 1643, he intended to help the traveller («peregrinantem», as he writes) in his journey, by providing clear directions about the land the wayfarer was headed to («versus quam Mundi plagam illi proficiscendum sit»).

Among the descriptions of Gallia, Hispania, Helvetia, Hungaria and many other European and even remote, far-away lands, Italy has a primary position, ancient and illustrious as it was («inter Europae regiones celeberrima»). And, at the very heart of Italy, the following lines are devoted to Norcia and its renowned Apennine Sibyl:

«NORCIA, which lies by the lake. Here many tales are told about the Sibyl, concealed in her cave. Publius Vergilius Maro calls the town “wintry”, owing to the elevation of the surrounding mountains (which are always capped with snow and engulf the neighbouring land with extreme cold)».

[In the original Latin text: «NURSIA, sita ad lacum. Hic multae sunt fabulae de Sibylla, in antro recondita. Virgilius eam frigidam civitatem vocat, propter montium circumjectorum (qui nivibus perpetuo occupantur frigusque ingens propinquis locis conciliant) altitudinem.»]

Fig. 27 - The Apennine Sibyl in David Froelich's *Viatorii liber* (Ulm, 1643)

Norcia by a lake, a clear reference to the Lake of Pilatus, once known as the Lake of Norcia. Norcia as the land of the Sibyl. A match that will last for hundreds of years, up to the twentieth century.

3.7 The Apennine Sibyl at the end of the eighteenth century: Giuseppe Colucci

A most interesting mention is provided by Giuseppe Colucci, a scholar and historian from the province of Marche, at the end of the eighteenth century: an age in which the ancient charming attractiveness of the Apennine Sibyl's legend was experiencing a significant fading, as Illuminism continued to assert the primacy of Reason with respect to old tales that were now

considered as empty babbles, only credited by gullible shepherds and peasants.

Within his extensive work presenting the illustrious antiquities of his native land, Colucci edited and published the manuscript containing Nicola Peranzoni's *De Laudibus Piceni*, written more than two hundred fifty years earlier, as we already saw in a previous paragraph.

Colucci's edition contains a number of annotated remarks, which accompany the main text written by Peranzoni: so, as we read Peranzoni's word about the Apennine Sibyl and the Lake of Pilate, we have also the chance to peruse the notes included by Colucci, which represent the vision that a man of letters living in the final portion of the eighteenth century had, at that late time, with relation to the Sibyl of the Apennines and the Roman prefect buried in an Apennine lake.

Giuseppe Colucci cannot but express his utter scorn for the popular legends which inhabited Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl:

«[...] this sort of puppet of a Sibyl made the credulous populace to believe that there the Sibyl inhabited, and dwelled in that cavern, in that hollow, and as such she was unattainable; and anybody in search of a forbidden contact would be heavily beaten; and scores and scores of further fairy tales, which the old women sitting before the fireplace, spinning and weaving, used to tell to guileless children; and naive people used to imagine as real, actual facts, handing those tales over from father to son, especially during the centuries in which ignorance ruled, and mist. But today all this does not happen anymore: even though some fake opinion still persists, that a Sibyl had ever lived under that mountain, nobody now believes anymore (at least if he's not a simpleton) that the dreamed-of Sibyl might really go about that countryside».

[In the original Italian text: «[...] questo fantoccio della Sibilla, ha dato motivo a gente credula di sospettare che là abitasse la Sibilla, che vivesse in quell'antro, in quella caverna, che fosse perciò inaccessibile, che a chi si fosse accostato più oltre di quello si poteva, toccavano delle fiere percosse, e cento e mille altre favolette, che le vecchie al fuoco filando raccontavano a' creduli bambocci; e che gente ignorante ha creduto per cose vere e reali, e di padre in figlio si sono tramandate, specialmente nei secoli

dell'ignoranza, e della caligine. Ma ai tempi presenti non accade più questo: se pure rimane qualche falsa opinione, che in quella montagna abbia vissuto la Sibilla, niuno più crede (almeno se non è sciocco) che presentemente passeggi per quelle contrade la sognata Sibilla»].

14081 Prima d'ogn' altra cosa sarebbe da questionarsi se queste Sibille sieno state mai al mondo, come alcuni non senza fondamento di ragione han dubitato. Ma ammessa l'esistenza di queste Sibille non abbiamo noi alcuna prova, che una o più di loro sia stata nella Montagna di M. Monaco detta tuttavia della Sibilla. Questa casuale denominazione, che da tutt' altro può esser derivata, che da questo fantoccio della Sibilla, ha dato motivo a gente credula di sospettare che là abitasse la

Sibilla, che vivesse in quell'antro, in quella caverna, che fosse perciò inaccessibile, che a chi si fosse accostato più oltre di quello si poteva, toccavano delle fiere percosse, e cento e mille altre favolette, che le vecchie al fuoco filando raccontavano a' creduli bambocci; e che gente ignorante ha creduto per cose vere e reali, e di padre in figlio si sono tramandate, specialmente nei secoli dell'ignoranza, e della caligine. Ma ai tempi presenti non accade più questo: se pure rimane qualche falsa opinione, che in quella montagna abbia vissuto la Sibilla, niuno più crede (almeno se non è sciocco) che presentemente passeggi per quelle contrade la sognata Sibilla. Chi desidera saper più cose di tali favole, vegga Fr. Leandro Alberti descriz. d' Italia pag. 249., che ne parla a lungo, e le smentisce.

Fig. 28 - Notes written by Giuseppe Colucci on the Apennine Sibyl from Colucci's edition of Niccolò Peranzoni's *De laudibus Piceni sive Marchiae Anconitanae Libellus* (Fermo, 1792), Tomo XXV, p. 118-119

No gentler words are written by Colucci with reference to the legend concerning the Lake of Pilate:

«Among those silly peasants who inhabit that land a foolish superstition spread itself, that no stone is to be thrown at the center of the lake for they say it would immediately raise a storm out of the offense which the corpse of Pilate would receive from that act; that same body which the people, with equal dullness, they think was submerged and dumped there».

[In the original Italian text: «È prevalsa presso quelli idioti contadini di quelle parti la sciocca credenza di non potersi gettare alcun sasso nel centro di quel lago, perché dicono che sarebbe causa di far nascer subito una tempesta per l'insulto che ne riceverebbe il corpo di Pilato, che con eguale sciocchezza credono colà immerso ed affondato»].

In our paper *Pontius Pilate and the shape of the waters* (2020), we presented a thorough recap of all available information about the Lake of Pilate, nested within the glacial cirque of Mount Vettore, and its peculiar shape, changing with seasons, rainwater levels and snowfalls. In that paper we did not include Colucci's contribution to the topic, featuring a beautiful, detailed description of the valley which runs from Mount Vettore to Mount Sibyl, the result of the grinding action performed by a vanished glacier:

«So in the Apennine mountains, and namely between the elevated mount of Vettore and that of the Sibyl, nature created a huge valley, on the top of which, at the point where the two mounts join and get connected, a sort of shell is present, in which all the waters of the rains and melting snows fall and gather together, also flowing from the cliffs and ravines. All those waters, coming together in the said shell [...] make up a wide lake in the middle of the valley; on its eastern side the lake has the high peak of Mount Vettore, on the western side that of the Sibyl; this latter mount presents frightful, gigantic, vertical cliffs, that when seen from below raise terror in one's heart, as they seem to be on the verge of tumbling suddenly down to plunge into the lake».

[In the original Italian text: «Adunque nei monti Apennini, e positivamente fra l'alta montagna di Vittore, e quella della Sibilla si forma dalla natura una gran valle, a capo della quale, dove le dette due montagne si uniscono, e si legano insieme, formasi una conchiglia, dove vanno a cadere, e si uniscono tutte le acque piovane, e delle nevi, che si struggono in esse montagne, come pure quelle delli scogli, e dei fossi delle medesime. Tutte queste grandi acque raccolte in detta conchiglia [...] formano nel mezzo della valle formano uno spazioso lago; il quale da oriente ha l'alta cima della montagna di Vittore, e all'occidente quella della Sibilla; la quale forma da questa parte orride insieme e smisurate rupi perpendicolari, che riguardandosi di sotto fanno orrore, parendo, che a tutti i momenti si vogliano slacciare per sprofondarsi in esso lago»].

Fig. 29 - Notes written by Giuseppe Colucci on the geography of the Sibillini Mountain Range from Colucci's edition of Niccolò Peranzoni's *De laudibus Piceni sive Marchiae Anconitanae Libellus* (Fermo, 1792), Tomo XXV, p. 121

After providing valuable information on the size and potential depth of the Lake of Pilate as it could be seen at the end of the eighteenth century (500 palms width and 3,500 palms circumference, corresponding to 100 meters and 770 meters, with a palm equalling nearly 22 centimeters), Giuseppe Colucci illustrates the peculiar spectacles-like shape of the waters:

«On the contrary, in summers, when waters are scant, the lake shrinks and in the middle a sort of chokepoint appears, which separates the two smaller,

round lakes forming the spectacles-like shape; there an islet is then formed, and it is like if they were two distinct lakes, even though for a small section to the west they never part completely and they share their waters, In this islet, when people can safely reach in summers, a few stones are found, in which intrigued wayfarers left their names in carvings».

[In the original Italian text: «All'incontro la state, mancando la copia di esse acque si restringe, e nel mezzo dove resta come una strozzatura, che divide i due tondi dei descritti occhiali formasi come un'isoletta, e pare che sieno due laghi, che per picciolo tratto verso occidente, dove non avviene che mai si distacchi del tutto si comunicano insieme le acque. In quest'isoletta, dove l'estate si può andare con sicurezza, Vi sono alcuni sassi, nei quali alcuni curiosi viaggiatori hanno lasciato scolpito il nome loro»].

Fig. 30 - Notes written by Giuseppe Colucci on the Apennine Sibyl from Colucci's edition of Niccolò Peranzoni's *De laudibus Piceni sive Marchiae Anconitanae Libellus* (Fermo, 1792), Tomo XXV, p. 122

This is a further attestation to the attractive might of this fascinating place, confirming Antoine de la Sale's fifteenth-century's account about the presence of an islet at the center of the Lake of Pilate and the visits being carried out, across many centuries, to the icy waters set amid the vertiginous cliffs of Mount Vettore, in central Italy.

4. Other miscellaneous references

In this chapter we present a few other references, which do not provide further direct mentions of the Sibillini Mountain Range's legendary tradition; nonetheless they feature a close connection with some of the themes that are present in the legends of the Sibyl's Cave and Pilate's Lake.

4.1 The Matter of Britain and Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*

In our paper *Antoine de la Sale and the magical bridge concealed beneath Mount Sibyl* (2018) we presented for the first time ever a full recap of the illustrious literary lineage of the magically narrow bridge which, according to Antoine de la Sale and his fifteenth-century *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, is staged in the deepest bowels of the Sibyl's Cave:

«Then you find a bridge, made of some unknown material, but it is said to be less than a single foot wide and it seems to be extending far ahead. [...] Yet as soon as you put both feet on the bridge, it becomes large enough; and the more you step ahead, the more it widens and the abyss becomes shallower» [in the original French text: «Lors trouve-l'on ung pont, que on ne scet de quoy il est, mais est advis qu'il n'est mie ung pied de large et semble estre moult long. [...] Mais aussitost que on a les deux pieds sur le pont, il est assez large; et tant va on plus avant et plus est large et moins creux»].

In that paper we showed that the bridge is presented in the *Tractatus de Purgatorio Sancti Patricii*, in a number of medieval *Visions* of Irish origin, and also in the *Dialogues* written by Pope St. Gregory I the Great in the sixth century A.D. Furthermore, various forms of 'test bridges' and other similar devices providing access to supernatural regions can be retrieved in many chivalric poems and romances.

A further example, which we did not mention in our article, is present in one of the most famous literary works belonging to the Matter of Britain: Thomas Malory's *Le Mort d'Arthur*, published in London in 1485, the

fundamental romance, written in English, that fostered the diffusion and fortune of the Arthurian cycle for the subsequent centuries.

Fig. 31 - A page from the original printed edition of Thomas Malory's *Le Mort d'Arthur* published by William Caxton (London, 1485), from one of the only two surviving copies (Morgan Library & Museum, New York)

We find our magical bridge at the very beginning of William Caxton's printed edition (Book 1 *The tale of King Arthur*, Chapter II *Balin or the Knight with the Two Swords*). We will follow here the text drawn from the original manuscript found in Winchester in 1934 and preserved at the British Library (Add. MS 59678), as transcribed by Eugène Vinaver:

«Than Merlion lette make a brygge of iron and of steele into that ilonde, and hit was but halff a foote brode, and there shall never man passe that brygge nother have hardynesse to go over hit but yf he were a passynge good man withoute trechery or vylany».

So we have an island and a metal bridge made up by the wizardly arts of Merlin, and the bridge is half-a-foot wide, and it can be passed only by a man who is true and guileless.

THE WORKS OF
Sir Thomas Malory

EDITED BY
EUGÈNE VINAVER

Geoffrey Cumberlege
OXFORD UNIVERSITY PRESS
LONDON NEW YORK TORONTO
1954

Than Merlion lette make a brygge of iron and of steele into that ilonde, and hit was but halff a foote brode, 'and there shall never man passe that brygge nother have hardynesse to go over hit but yf he were a passynge good man withoute trechery or vylany.' Also the scawberd off Balyns swerde Merlion lefte hit on thys syde the ilonde,

Fig. 32 - The magical bridge as it appears in *Le Mort d'Arthur*, from the transcript edited by Eugène Vinaver (London, 1954), p. 70

The bridge is intended to magically protect the scabbard of Balin's sword, which is left by Merlin on the island for Galahad to find («that Galaad sholde fynde hit»). It is a further example of a 'testing device' providing an access to an enchanted/supernatural place only if the wayfarer is a pure, unblemished soul.

So, once again, we see that the contrivance of a magically narrow bridge is not an original creation developed within the legendary tradition of the Sibillini Mountain Range, as it may appear when reading *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* by Antoine de la Sale; instead, as a matter of fact this fascinating device is marked by a much longer story and is also fully present amid the many themes which are staged in the context of the Matter of Britain.

4.2 Mount Vettore's 'Road of Fairies': another superimposed legendary layer (from the Italian Alps)

Readers of *The chthonian legend* paper may remember that the article also contains a description of the 'Road of Fairies', the popular name assigned to the huge, terrific fault line which splits horizontally the western side of Mount Vettore for its entire length.

Fig. 33 - Mount Vettore with the 'Road of Fairies'

The titanic fracture is the results of thousands of years of earthquakes and illustrates with the utmost might the visible potency of seismic waves in the region.

Despite all that, as we already said, no one has never been able to link the legends about a Sibyl and a Roman prefect, present in the area, to the peculiar seismic behaviour of this land.

The same local population who lives in the area used to associate the streak on Mount Vettore with a different narrative, thus moving further away from the possible chance of stumbling into a potential, even though conjectural, truth.

In fact, according to the silly populace the streak on the mountain is a trail left by the Sibyl's cortege of fairies, as reported by Paolo Toschi in 1967: «One certain evening the fairies, whose queen was the Sibyl, asked for

permission to attend the night dances [...] Suddenly, the horizon began to gleam with the first glow of dawn. Startled, dismayed and overwhelmed by apprehension and fear, they rushed into a frantic run towards the cave. [...] A whole streak on the mountain, along the side of Mount Vettore, was so trampled with the frenzied hurry of the fairies, that the trail they followed is still visible today».

Is this an original legend, born right here where the central Apennines raise their most elevated peak?

Let's remember that the Sibyl was not original (she's a character coming from the Matter of Britain), and neither was Pontius Pilate (a narrative arising from the first centuries of Christianity).

The 'Road of Fairies' makes no exception.

If we take the Bulletin edited by the Italian Alpine Club in 1886 (Vol. XX, no. 53), we find an interesting article, whose title is *The Legends of the Alps*:

«From one of those shepherd, an elderly man who had always been living amid the mountains, I heard about Mount Civrari the tale, told with an unsurpassable efficacy, on one of the legends which once were so popular, and now are fading away in that portion of the Alps; and this is the tale which recalls the 'Race of Fairies'»]

[In the original Italian text: «Da uno di questi pastori, invecchiato fra le montagne, udii sul Civrari narrare, con un'efficacia insuperabile, una delle leggende che furono popolari ed ora vanno perdendosi in quella parte delle Alpi, ed è quella che ricorda la Corsa delle fate»].

Mount Civrari is not set amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, in central Italy: it's a peak of the Italian Alps, in the province of Piedmont, northern Italy. But the folk tale has many points of contact with that living between Umbria and Marche:

Fig. 34 - Maria Savi Lopez, *Legends of the Alps*, in *Bollettino del Club Alpino Italiano per l'anno 1886* (Vol. XX, n. 53), p. 191

«One night, amid that barrenness, while perhaps the fog ran rapidly through the gorges, in the moonlight, the wind lashing against the rocks [...], the old shepherd, dismayed by a noise of wheels and rattles, went out from his bleak shelter and saw the gorgeous, wondrous Race of fairies».

[In the original Italian text: «Di notte, in mezzo a quella desolazione, mentre forse la nebbia passava rapidamente nelle gole, fra il chiarore della luna ed il vento che flagellava le rocce [...], il vecchio pastore, sgomentato da un rumore di ruote e di sonagli, era uscito dalla povera casa ed aveva visto passare la splendida e meravigliosa Corsa delle fate»].

Le Leggende delle Alpi

I. Alpigiani e fate.

Parmi che le leggende siano una splendida o bizzarra poesia del passato, rimasta nella coscienza popolare, come ricordo di antichi drammi, di storiche imprese o di credenze che forse misero lo spavento fra altre generazioni.

Molte di esse ebbero origine antichissima, quando non ancora la grave parola della storia andava ricordando i casi delle genti nuove, e le prime gesta dei padri nostri. Allora intorno alle tradizioni lasciate dagli avi come prezioso retaggio, la fantasia popolare mise, con un vero diletto, il fascino di casi misteriosi e soprannaturali; ma non dobbiamo solo ad essa la creazione delle leggende più note nell'antichità, poichè dall'India all'Egitto, dalla Persia alla Fenicia, le caste privilegiate o i sacerdoti delle misteriose divinità, nel desiderio di nascondere innanzi al volgo quanto avrebbe dovuto essere il retaggio scientifico e storico dell'intera nazione, andarono inventando dei racconti che diedero origine a molte leggende.

Anche i poeti, avvalendosi di splendide immagini, mentre narravano qualche fatto storico importante, o vedevano in ogni forza ed in ogni forma della materia una divinità malefica o gentile, furono non di rado creatori di nuove leggende che divennero rapidamente popolari, e rimasero tali nel volger dei secoli. Poi, come se l'orgoglio degli uomini, che volevano il monopolio della scienza, l'amore dei popoli per racconti meravigliosi, ed anche la calda fantasia dei poeti, non bastassero per travisare la realtà dei fatti, spesso avvenne che l'amor patrio o l'orgoglio, cercando di sublimare le origini di un popolo, di una città, o forse di una famiglia chiamata al comando supremo, resero più incomprensibili ancora le oscure tradizioni, o crearono nuove leggende; mentre ignoravasi che verrebbe l'ora in cui la storia, trionfando su tanti errori antichi, cercherebbe l'uomo sotto l'usbergo sfolgorante del l'eroe leggendario, o troverebbe negli Dei fondatori d'illustri città, dei poveri guerrieri nomadi, desiosi di stabile dimora, o dei pastori stanchi della vita errante.

Da uno di questi pastori, invecchiato fra le montagne, udii sul Civrari narrare, con un'efficacia insuperabile, una delle leggende che furono popolari ed ora vanno perdendosi in quella parte delle Alpi, ed è quella che ricorda la *Corsa delle fate*.

Di notte, in mezzo a quella desolazione, mentre forse la nebbia passava rapidamente nelle gole, fra il chiarore della luna ed il vento che flagellava le roccie, coprendo la voce monotona del Richiaglio, il vecchio pastore, sgomentato da un rumore di ruote e di sonagli, era uscito dalla povera casa ed aveva visto passare la splendida e meravigliosa *Corsa delle fate*.

Fig. 35 - The race of fairies from *Legends of the Alps*, in *Bollettino del Club Alpino Italiano per l'anno 1886* (Vol. XX, n. 53), p. 196

The article's author, Maria Savi Lopez, an Italian writer and poet, provides a description of this magical, illusory race:

«[...] the old man described the vision he beheld that night [...] he saw a cortege of fairies adorned with crowns of alpine flowers, standing on chariots of fire, in a radiance of light, followed by sprites in their vertiginous race across the crests, the hills and the lofty peaks».

[In the original Italian text: «[...] il vecchio descriveva la visione apparsagli in quella notte [... in cui poté] veder passare le fate colle corone di edelweiss, ritte sui carri di fuoco, in uno splendore di luce, seguite dai folletti nella corsa vertiginosa su le creste, i colli e le altissime cime»].

According to Savi Lopez, this sort of narrative is present in other areas of the Italian Alps as well, and even on the Austrian side:

«In this credence concerning the night walks of the fairies amid our Western Alps [...] we find a significant relation with other beliefs which still last across the whole alpine chain, and especially in the area of Tyrol and the Austrian regions, where a vivid memory of Goddess Bercht is retained. [...] They say that, from Christmas to Epiphany, the goddess enshrouded in radiant light flies over the mountains, with her court of faires and witches, and collects the offerings that the local inhabitants leave on the roofs of their houses. Many of those fairies are ugly in their

countenance and use long sticks and bags, in which they stow the received gifts. In their race they make lots of leaps».

[In the original Italian text: «In questa credenza nella passeggiata notturna delle fate sulle nostre Alpi Graie [...] trovasi molta relazione con altre credenze che durano ancora in tutta la catena delle Alpi, e specialmente verso il Tirolo e le regioni austrache, ove si ha viva memoria della dea Bercht. [...] Esse narrano che, specialmente da Natale all'Epifania, la dea splendente di viva luce passa sulle montagne, e col suo seguito di fate e di streghe va raccogliendo le offerte che gli alpigiani depongono sui tetti delle case. Molte di queste fate sono orribili nell'aspetto, ed hanno lunghi bastoni e sacchi ove mettono i doni. Nel loro viaggio fanno un'infinità di salti»].

And the peasant's dance's theme is also present:

«Maybe as a last recollection of the holidays that they used to celebrate in lost ages as a tribute to the mighty goddess, it is still in use amid certain inhabitants of the Alps a dance bearing the goddess' name. Yet the dance itself has nothing peculiar in the steps of the four performing dancers, who wear rich red-and-yellow garments, adorned with ribbons, and also a feathered crown».

[In the original Italian text: «Forse come ultimo ricordo delle feste che si dovettero celebrare nei tempi lontani, in onore della potente dea, si usa ancora fra certi alpigiani una danza che prende il suo nome. Questa però non ha nulla di speciale nei movimenti dei quattro ballerini che l'eseguiscono, i quali sono vestiti con abiti ricchissimi di color giallo e rosso, adorni con nastri, e portano una corona di penne»].

To make the affinity even more straight, here is the alpine goddess in her subterranean abode:

«On the Swiss Alps people believe that the parade of fairies takes place on the second day of the new year, or the third if the year begins with a Saturday; but in winters the handsome goddess has her queenly chair under the earth, where her cortege is also to be found; yet she comes from time to time back on earth, attired in rich clothes, throwing rye on the mountain's small fields; or, on Christmas, dressed like a hunter, she goes running

followed by a party of rejoicing sprites, and she protects and preserves the good maidens».

Sulle Alpi della Svizzera, credesi che la processione delle fate avvenga nel secondo giorno dell'anno, o nel terzo, se l'anno comincia di sabato; però nell'inverno la bella dea ha il suo trono sottoterra, ove trovasi

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pure il suo gregge; ma essa ritorna anche qualche volta sulla terra, vestita con indicibile ricchezza, e gitta della segala sui campicelli delle montagne, o a Natale vestita da cacciatrice corre seguita da una folla di spiriti allegri, ed è speciale protettrice delle buone fanciulle.

Fig. 36 - The race of a subterranean goddess and her fairies from *Legends of the Alps*, in *Bollettino del Club Alpino Italiano per l'anno 1886* (Vol. XX, n. 53), p. 197-198

[In the original Italian text: «Sulle Alpi della Svizzera, credesi che la processione delle fate avvenga nel secondo giorno dell'anno, o nel terzo, se l'anno comincia di sabato; però nell'inverno la bella dea ha il suo trono sottoterra, ove trovasi pure il suo gregge; ma essa ritorna anche qualche volta sulla terra, vestita con indicibile ricchezza, e gitta della segala sui campicelli delle montagne, o a Natale vestita da cacciatrice corre seguita da una folla di spiriti allegri, ed è speciale protettrice delle buone fanciulle»].

So it is clear that the fairies merrily racing across Mount Vettore are just one of the many superpositions of legends we have been able to identify amid the Sibillini Mountain Range: just like the Sibyl and Pontius Pilate, the 'Road of Fairies' is but a reminiscence of an extraneous folklore coming from different, far-away mountains, typical of the inhabitants of the Italian and Austrian Alps. The fault line has just represented a suitable - and most impressive - scenario on which to stage a tale of racing sprites, which has nothing to do not only with the earthquakes (the originators of the fracture on the mountain) but also with the Apennine Sibyl, whose lineage can be traced back to the Matter of Britain.

This is further example of the stunning superposition of legendary material that lives on the elevated, appalling peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range: a perfect setting to attract foreign tales and myths of different sorts and origin.

But the primary myth is hidden down below, under the many layers of superimposed legends. And the deepest layer is earthquakes.

4.3 The Catholic Church and the Apennine Sibyl

Since Antoine de la Sale's remark on a Pope who «filled up» and «dismantled» the entryway to the Sibyl's Cave so as to prevent any visit to the site, the attention of the Catholic Church to the legendary traditions of the Sibillini Mountain Range has always been keen, owing to the unholy, fiendish nature of the rituals performed by wicked, not-well-intentioned visitors at the Cave and at the Lake of Pilate as well.

We must also remember that the first mention known to scholars about the Lake is the fourteenth-century excerpt retrieved in Petrus Berchorius, who got to know of the necromantic character of those waters near Norcia «by a certain prelate, a trustworthy person indeed among all men»: a member of the Church of that age.

And we must not forget the ecclesiastic «criminal trial» held in Paris in 1587 against two sorcerers who had been so bold as to reach Mount Sibyl to carry out their evil consecrations, as narrated by Pierre Crespet: «the Pope», he says, «had the said cave, where the said Sibyl dwells, carefully guarded to prevent any contact with her».

Apart from the listed historical attestations to the observation and scrutiny of the sibilline phenomenon maintained by the ecclesiastical institutions over time, today a sensation persists that the contemporary Church still 'keeps an eye' on the Apennine Sibyl's legendary tradition and related hustle and bustle. In fact, even though we are now living in an age of secularization and empty churches, a careful watch is maintained over the potential morons who could eventually dream of a foolish revival of demonic cults at the Sibyl's mountain-top or Pilate's Lake.

où il ſouhaittoit eſtre trāſporté moyēnāt que
le vent ne fuſt contraire. Dit dauātage que le
Pape fait ſoigneuſement garder ladicte carrie
re où eſt ladicte Sibylle, pour empēſcher la cō-
municatiō avec elle, & n'ya que ceux qui ſōt
magiciēs, & y peuuēt inuiſiblemēt entrer qui
la puisſēt aborder, à cauſe que quād on cōmu-
nique avec elle, ſoyt magiciē ou autre, les tē-

Fig. 37 - The Sibyl's cave guarded, from Pierre Crespet (Crespetus), *De la hayne de Satan et malins
esprist contro l'homme* (Paris, 1590), p. 93

As an instance of this attention, we quote from a speech delivered by H.E. Renato Boccardo, Archbishop of the ecclesiastic district of Spoleto - Norcia, during the *XIX Pastoral Workshop Pilgrimage: Faith and Beauty* held in Rome in 2017. Boccardo, in his address describing the wounds ingenerated by the earthquakes on the cultural and artistic heritage of the area, presents its administrated territory with the following significant words:

«Our archdiocese extends in the very heart of Apennines, across a territory which in antiquity stretched out far beyond the present borders, as it reached as far as Marche and Abruzzo. A hard, harsh land, commanded by the mountains of the Sibyl...».

[In the original Italian text: «La nostra Archidiocesi si estende nel cuore dell'Appennino, in un territorio che anticamente andava ben oltre i confini attuali, raggiungendo le Marche e l'Abruzzo. Un territorio difficile, aspro, dominato dai monti della Sibilla...»].

That's only a quote, a mere mention about the Sibyl, included in a sentence which is apparently marked by a casual taste; and yet the Sibyl is there, now as it was in antiquity, in the words of Boccardo. And still she seems to loom over the peaceful inhabitants of the place, with a shadow that has never faded away. So much so that the Archbishop of our present times still feels the need to remind his audience, in the year 2017, that this land is not completely normal, as a weird companion is always lurking there, in the deep cave hidden beneath a windy, vertiginous crest.

La nostra Archidiocesi si estende nel cuore dell'Appennino, in un territorio che anticamente andava ben oltre i confini attuali, raggiungendo le Marche e l'Abruzzo. Un territorio difficile, aspro, dominato dai monti della Sibilla, che sorprende il viandante dopo ogni curva con piani ondulati e dolcissimi, come quelli di Castelluccio o di Colfiorito. Un territorio che ha una fisionomia artistica particolare come il suo paesaggio, anzi ad esso strettamente legata, il risultato unico e irripetibile

Fig. 38 - H.E. Renato Boccardo's remarks on the Sibyl, from *La bellezza ferita*, in *XIX Pastoral Workshop Pilgrimage: Faith and Beauty* (Rome, 2017), p. 3

And a further attestation of interest by the Church I can personally set forward. On August 17th 2018, in Montegallo, I delivered a presentation session and speech on the legendary tradition of the Apennine Sibyl, right beneath the most frightful slopes of Mount Vettore, the highest mountain in the Sibillini Mountain Range. Sitting amid the audience, which included lovers of the legendary tale and people who were interested in gaining more insight on this myth, I was honored to notice the presence of His Excellency Monsignor Giovanni D'Ercole, at that time the Bishop of Ascoli Piceno, who was in Montegallo for an official visit lasting from August, 15 to 23, in a land which was so magnificent but also so hardly hit by the recent earthquakes.

Monsignor D'Ercole silently listened to the whole session. When it was over, he quietly left. But he had been considering each single word I had pronounced about that ancient legend, which certainly could not disown its original demonic character.

So the Catholic Church is always there, on the alert. A centuries-old confrontation, which still goes on though in a low tone. Even in our present epoch of Internet, smartphones and artificial intelligence.

5. *Personal considerations of an imaginative researcher*

In this section of the present paper we quit the fields of philological and geomythological research to enter a more personal realm, with a view to leaving the readers with a number of notes and considerations, marked by subjective tones, illustrating the genesis of our research into the legends of the Sibillini Mountains.

And we start from the final part: reception.

5.1 *The chthonian legend: the academic reception*

What happened after March, 25th 2020, in the wake of the public release of the paper *Sibillini Mountain Range, the chthonian legend*?

What sort of widespread diffusion and acceptance has this research experienced in the wake of the publications of so momentous a result? What was the reaction of the research community, in Italy and abroad?

The answer is simple: basically none. Nothing, absolutely nothing happened.

And - actually - nothing was expected to happen, as the author of the *The Chthonian legend* - an independent researcher, an outsider - is not a member of any academic institution.

So nobody from the international academic milieu ever contacted this Author (if not privately and in a limited number of cases), and no formal cooperation proposal in research was ever put forward.

Yet something incredible happened. And it's still happening.

Starting from year 2020, “Michele Sanvico”, with his many papers concerning the Sibillini Mountain Range's legendary heritage, has turned into one of the most-read scientific researchers on two main academic social networks, connecting hundreds of thousands of professional scholars around the world.

For Academia.edu, the international web-based platform for sharing academic research (265 million registered users, 55 million uploaded papers as of July 2024), Michele Sanvico is «a highly followed author». Because, incredibly enough, Michele Sanvico's research places at the «Top 4%» of all Academia.edu researchers!

The image shows two parts of the Academia.edu interface. The top part is a banner for a paper titled "Sibilla Appenninica, Il Mistero e La Leggenda - La Grotta Della Sibilla: Ciò Che Sappiamo" by Michele Sanvico. The banner highlights the author as "A highly followed author" and shows a snippet of the paper's text. The bottom part shows the user profile for Michele Sanvico, including a search bar, a profile picture, and statistics: 204 Followers, 27 Following, and 8,998 Public Views (Top 4%).

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...oso della grotta era ancora visibile: una cavità buia sotto l'impetosa luce solare che inondava la **vetta** a mezzogiorno, una condizione quasi insopportabile per gli uomini impegnati in quella rischiosa spedi...

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Fig. 39 - Michele Sanvico as a «highly followed author» in the «Top 4%» according to the Academia.edu social network

Thousand and thousands of researchers, belonging to major academic institutions from all around the world, read one or more of Michele

Sanvico's several papers on the Sibillini Mountain Range, its legendary traditions, Mount Sibyl, the lake of Pilate and the innovative conjecture about a connection between the legends and the peculiar seismic behaviour of the territory.

Within ResearchGate.net, a more selective network connecting 25 million researchers around the world (mainly with official affiliations to academic institutions), this Author totaled more than 34,000 reads, of which nearly 5,000 full text reads, and reached a 'Research Interest Score' of 71.9, higher than 59% of all ResearchGate members!

Unbelievable as it may appear, in addition to that Sanvico's score is higher than 92% of all researchers working in the field of Classical Philology, and more than 85% of scholars involved in Cultural History and Mythology & Folklore.

This result is even more significant if we consider that, though unaffiliated to any professional academic institution, your Author was accepted by ResearchGate.net as a member of this prominent network after an evaluation of the quality of the proposed articles and original research topics.

But how can all this be possible?

Sure enough it is not so usual to see an independent, freelance researcher bounce up to a high-level ranking amid a multitude of professional, world-class scholars, researchers and scientists.

As a matter of fact the reason for this lies in the original character of the proposed research, insufficiently covered or even totally uncovered by other scholars, so that large space proved to be available for the publication of dedicated papers.

And the papers seem to be of great interest for international researchers: the first mentions are starting to flow in, with a first quote from scholars at the Stanford University and a second from an illustrious member of the Royal Danish Library in Copenhagen. We can suppose that, in the years to come, more quotes will appear in the scientific literature, if we consider that many

readers of the Apennine Sibyl's papers are post-doc and PhD students, who are about to publish their own papers within the next decade.

The screenshot shows the top of a ResearchGate profile for Michele Sanvico. At the top left is the ResearchGate logo. To its right is a search bar with the placeholder text "Search for publications, researchers, or questions". Below the search bar is a breadcrumb trail: "Home > Michele Sanvico". The profile header features a circular profile picture of Michele Sanvico, his name "Michele Sanvico", and his title "Independent Researcher" and field "Physics". Below the header are three tabs: "About", "Publications" (with a badge showing "55"), and "Network". The "About" tab is selected, and the content below shows two statistics: "55 Publications" and "34,744 Reads" (with an information icon).

Fig. 40 - Michele Sanvico's profile in the ResearchGate.net web portal

As a conclusive remark to the present paragraph, I want to stress the fact that, although the publication process of the whole set of papers belonging to the series *The Apennine Sibyl, a Mystery and a Legend* took some five years, with the most important section being published in March, 25th 2020, care was taken lest the main 'research idea' be 'used' by others while the publication process was still ongoing.

In fact, the utmost attention was paid to enshroud the core result of the investigation (i.e. the original and unprecedented conjecture concerning the link between the Apennine Sibyl and the peculiar seismic behaviour of the Sibillini Mountain Range) into a veil of mystery and anticipation, as paper publication progressed from the first ones in 2017 to the main article of March, 2020. No reference to earthquakes was ever included in the papers being released one after the other before 2020, leaving the final, breakthrough step of the research hidden to everybody until the occurrence of the final public discovery with *The chthonian legend* article.

This prevented any other researcher to capitalise on the ongoing investigation, and, in the end, left to the Author of the present article the full control and authorship of the significant scientific results which were finally obtained.

A very long process, which ultimately led to a thorough ownership of the original research idea. And all happened in the complete absence of any affiliation to any university or research center, in a fully independent framework.

This is the strength of working alone, to achieve significant results under no external conditioning, with the total freedom to think 'outside the box'. A research position which is totally extraneous to the current, mainstream academic approach, in which the whole system works together, but the system does not render you free, nor it allows free thinking, because you must stick to the opinions and credences held by the organisation (including academic organisations) you are immersed in.

This concept was effectively expressed by Max Horkheimer, the German philosopher and sociologist, in his work *Eclipse of Reason* (Chapter IV):

«From the day of his birth, the individual is made to feel that there is only one way of getting along in this world [...] by imitation. He continuously responds to what he perceives about him, [...] emulating the traits and attitudes represented by all the collectivities that enmesh him - his play group, his classmates, his athletic team, and all the other groups that, as has been pointed out, enforce a more strict conformity, a more radical surrender through complete assimilation, than any father or teacher in the nineteenth century could impose. By echoing, repeating, imitating his surroundings, by adapting himself to all the powerful groups to which he eventually belongs, by transforming himself from a human being into a member of organizations, by sacrificing his potentialities for the sake of readiness and ability to conform to and gain influence in such organizations, he manages to survive».

His survival, adds Horkheimer, is achieved «by the oldest biological means of survival, namely, mimicry».

As an utterly independent researcher, I had to mimic nobody. So I could succeed where all others, across the centuries and up to our present time, had failed.

Fig. 41 - A first academic mention of a research article belonging to the series *The Apennine Sibyl, a Mystery and a Legend*

Pius II: *Orationes*.

- *Collected orations of Enea Silvio Piccolomini (Pope Pius II)*. Ed. and transl. by Michael von Cotta-Schoenberg. 12 vols. 2019.¹
 - 5: Oration “*Si putarem*.” COR, 2: 5.²

Rill, Bernd: *Friedrich III. Habsburgs europäischer Durchbruch*. 1987.

Sanvico, Michele: *The Apennine Sibyl, a Mystery and Legend. Pope Pius II Piccolomini's Original letter on the Sibyl's Cave published for the first time ever (with new findings)*. Article published on ResearchGate in 2018.

Sashalmi, Endre: *Aeneas Sylvius Piccolomini and the Hungarian Succession. A Humanist as a Spokesman for Ladislaus (Postnatus) V*. In: *Specimina Nova Pars Prima Sectio Mediaevalis*, 6 (2011) 163-173.

Saumaise, Claude: *De subscribendis et signandis testamentis*. 1553.

Solinus, Gajus Julius: *Collectanea mirabilium mundi*. Ed. Th. Mommsen. 1864.

Fig. 42 - Another academic mention

5.2 *The Chthonian Legend: the reception in the territory*

So far we have discussed the reception accorded by the academic milieu to the research which, in March 2020, established a new conjectural connection between the legendary heritage of the Sibillini Mountain Range and the earthquakes that recursively use to hit this central-Italian territory.

But what sort of reception has this research experienced amid the very same territories it was taking into consideration? What happened in Italy, in the regions of Marche and Umbria, and in the towns and villages encircling the magical crests of Mount Vettore and Mount Sibyl?

The answer is not dissimilar to the one already rendered as to academic reception: virtually nothing.

And it's not only a matter of virtuality. As a matter of fact, there was no response at all.

While the academic world responded somehow by expressing a keen interest at least in reading the papers I published on the subject, the local Italian institutions - including two regional administrations (Umbria and

Marche), a number of municipalities (Norcia, Montemonaco, Ascoli, and others), and a selected list of public authorities (Parco Nazionale dei Monti Sibillini) - never showed any sign of life.

Fig. 43 - Sibillini Mountain Range National Park, official logo

A most significant research, which potentially is re-writing the legendary history, if not history at all, of their own land seems to prove of no interest to the public sector.

It appears it's none of their business, although they claim to be deeply involved in promoting local tourism and traditions in the Sibillini Mountain Range area, by carrying out marketing and information campaigns amid the larger public, both in Italy and abroad.

However, nobody ever showed up to ask more information on this peculiar research, which solves an enigmatic riddle that has been in place for more than eight hundred years, since the first mention of a magical lake found in Petrus Berchorius' excerpt.

And what about the private sector and local investors? Hotels, resorts, restaurants, shops all around the Sibillini Mountains are striving to seize increasing market shares in term of tourist attendance and accommodated nights. But nobody likes earthquakes, and the talks over earthquakes neither, because fears arise that tourist might prefer to flee or desert altogether a country which is too prone to them. So nobody ever came to

ask for a further insight or to host a slide presentation on the potential link between seismic waves and the renowned legendary tales; and the few sessions held by your Author in the area went almost unattended.

That was really a nice reception for a work that tries to cast light on the Sibillini Mountains' inhabitants' origin and beliefs, up to their farthest ancestors.

So we are still waiting for them to wake up. For the time being, more than four years later, they are all still fast asleep.

5.3 The Chthonian legend: the origin

In this more personal chapter we like to include a brief summary of the winding road that ultimately led to *The Chthonian legend* article.

When did it all begin?

On August 16th, 2009 I decided to climb Mount Sibyl, in central Italy, for the first time in my life. I knew a legend lingered over that remote cliff, yet I did not know any detail of it. When I finally reached the remnants of the legendary cave, I made up my mind to get further insight on the old sinister story connected to the presence of a Sibyl. And - while I was descending the steep cliff to go back to my car - I began to fancy about a book: a brand new novel which would narrate about the Sibilline myth and retrieve unprecedented answers on that eerie mystery.

By a remarkable chance, when standing right on the mountain-top, I was approached by a TV crew working for the RAI national Italian broadcaster. That day was a main summer holiday in Italy, and the journalist was asking the trekkers why they were there and what they expected to see on the Sibyl's peak. So it was that I - the future author of *Abyssus Sibyllae - The Eleventh Sibyl* and future researcher into the sibilline myth - gave my first interview ever on the Sibyl's legend, having put down not a single line of my still-to-be-written book or not-yet-born research!

Fig. 44 - Future author Michele Sanvico interviewed by the national TV broadcaster on Mount Sibyl's peak in 2009

What the novel on the Sibyl would be about? I was stunned and disappointed at the vision of the entrance to the Sibyl's Cave, turned into a heap of broken boulders and rubble by some unknown hand at some unspecified time: what mystery was hidden there? And what was the story of those rocky debris silently lying on a remote Italian mountain-top? I began to see a plot that would have retraced the story of the Apennine Sibyl's legendary tale, with a touch of fiction that would rely on the imaginative conjecture that a second concealed entryway to the Cave existed somewhere on the Sibyl's cliff, still allowing an access to the ancient enigma only to initiated people.

So in a few months I wrote and released *Abyssus Sibyllae*, the Abyss of the Sibyl, in which the main character was plunged in a compelling research that started with Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* and Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* and probed into the centuries up to the ruinous excavations carried out by treasure hunters in the twentieth

century and the scientific inspections effected on Mount Sibyl's top in the year 2000.

In this book, of which I will talk more later in the following paragraphs, I unconsciously made the very same error I subsequently attributed to all scholars in the sibilline legendary matter: I did not considered the Lake of Pilate at all, as it seemed so me so silly a fairy tale, and so out-of-context owing to the mention of the famous Roman prefect of the Gospels, that I did not repute it may be of any interest. But - as I already illustrated - I was wrong, and actually a lot wrong.

Fig. 45 - The first, self-formatted cover of Michele Sanvico's novel *Abyssus Sibyllae* (2010)

Nonetheless, *Abyssus Sibyllae* already contained, in an odd, subterranean form, the appalling topic of the earthquake, though still not connected straightly to the Apennine Sibyl, and more in the form of a terrific vibration which dreadfully pulsed across the entire book and the town of Norcia, and would eventually blast off ten years later with *The Chthonian legend* paper.

«That was the force which throbbed in the unfathomed pits of the earth, under the square itself, so that present-day Norcia was only the most recent, shallowest layer of a quite older Norcia, rooted firmly to that very land whereon countless generations of men had been dwelling since timeless

ages. [...] An inhuman beast lived unseen under the ground, awaiting. Beneath the square and the streets and the ancient dwellings of men, the faceless being with gleaming, sightless eyes waited patiently, in a dream. Its dream, the dream of a dark subterranean potency lasted for whole lifetimes of men, looming over them as though heavy, rolling vapours announcing the coming of a storm; until, all of a sudden, the blind, faceless beast awoke, and manifested its cruel abomination across the surface of the earth».

This is how I sensed the mighty power of earthquakes always operating beneath the Sibillini Mountain Range. It was year 2010.

Many more years elapsed. On August 24th, 2016 a large earthquakes hit the southern borders of the Sibillini Mountain Range, claiming hundreds of lives. A further huge quake hit the town of Norcia on October 30th, 2016, of a magnitude ranking amid the most powerful earthquakes ever recorded in Italy.

Something was quivering in my mind, but still I did not know what it was exactly.

In 2017, while the ground was still trembling, I decided to launch a new Facebook page, *The Apennine Sibyl, a Mystery and a Legend*: it was initially intended as a mean to provide simple information to tourists on the legendary heritage of the Sibillini Mountains (and still with a special neglect for the Lake of Pilate), with no specific plans to develop any original research on the topic.

Fig. 46 - The Apennine Sibyl - A Mystery and a Legend (Facebook logo)

And yet some thing was still pulsating within my mind. I felt that something was completely wrong with all literary and philological research carried out on the Sibillini Mountain Range by all previous scholars, and published in the available publications: why had nobody searched for any mention of the Apennine Sibyl in the previous literature, in particular of the Middle Ages? Why did they all say that this Sibyl seemed to suddenly appear in the fifteenth century, as a lone star abruptly shining in the dark?

It seemed to me that it was incongruous: if that Sibyl's legend was so potent so as to cross many centuries after the fifteenth, certainly she had left traces also in previous centuries. I just needed to look for them.

My quest was immediately bountiful: at the end of 2017 I had already found lots of hints to episodes narrated in Andrea da Barberino's romance *Guerrino the Wretch* - which contains the earliest mention of the Sibyl of Norcia - in earlier chivalric poems, namely *Huon of Bordeaux* and *Huon d'Auvergne*. And further narratives later used by Antoine de la Sale in his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* I could retrieve in preceding literary works: the magical bridge and the ever-slamming doors were part of ancient legendary traditions, and were later included in the sibilline lore.

So it was becoming clear that a hundred fifty years of scholarly research had not been able to trace up the Apennine Sibyl to her manifest literary roots.

But the most thrilling part was still to come.

During the 2016/2017 Christmas holidays, as the earthquake continued to shake persistently the area of Norcia, residents there were strained to their utmost level of anguish, with their homes continually trembling and roaring noises ascending day and night from the bowels of the earth. Everybody was living in fear of another large blow, the final one that would destroy the whole land. My wife's relatives, from Norcia, all uttered on their phone call a same harrowed plea: «When will it all stop? When will the quake be appeased? Why it is so mean to us?».

Fig. 47 - Fractures on the western side of Mount Vettore generated by the 2016 seismic sequence

That was exactly the moment of a sort of enlightenment.

Today's residents were scared. They would do anything to stop the earthquake. They knew there was no effective way to stop it, because tectonic plates are gigantic natural structures beyond any human control. And yet they personified the seismic waves, they thought of them like a sort of monster and attributed to them evil intentions against their lives and souls.

If all that occurred to contemporary, twenty-first-century men and women, what had happened in similar contexts during Roman times, or even before, across the Iron Age?

In that very moment I fully understood the sheer terror that most probably used to seize the ancient inhabitants of the Sibillini Mountain Range. I could imagine them seeing the earthquake as a godly monster, a subterranean demon, a potency of the netherworld, in the total absence of any other explanation for what was happening to them. I could almost sense their craving for it to stop, their madness at the unrelenting shakes generated by a mighty seismic sequence.

For sure they would have looked for a way to appease the demon, by talking to it and possibly offering sacrifices to it. But where to find that subterranean beast?

The answer was plain. The Sibillini Mountain Range offered two places where to establish a contact with the demon: a horrible Cave, high above a mountainous cliff, and an eerie Lake, set between appalling ravines.

So here came the idea: the Cave and Lake had been - since the earliest antiquity - suitable places for talking to a world of subterranean gods, which were believed to preside over the earthquakes (which actually most often seemed to originate from those very spots). And across the subsequent centuries this sort of places would not lose their blood-curdling renown, attracting new layers of frightful narratives as the original tale about earthquakes faded away with time.

Once the main idea was formed, I decided not to disclose it straightforwardly by publishing it at once in one or more social networks.

It was too tasty an idea, not to be wasted through an immediate discovery. If I did so, certainly someone else would steal it and publish his/her own research paper by claiming full ownership for a most-interesting breakthrough conjecture that never before had been set forth. I didn't want to lose my primacy.

So my long journey across the legendary heritage of the Sibillini Mountain Range began to unfold across a compelling series of research papers, that were released one after another in a few years. During the year 2018 I elaborated a number of preliminary papers which just paved the way to a main fundamental breakthrough, achieved at the beginning of 2019 with the paper *Birth of a Sibyl: the medieval connection*: the first, ever-released research that fully highlighted the medieval lineage of the Apennine Sibyl, an offspring of Morgan le Fay and her companion Sebile, two main characters belonging to the Matter of Britain. Nobody had ever stated that so clearly, apart from selected scholars which had dealt with the matter only on an incidental basis.

At that time my 'close relationship' with the Apennine Sibyl was fully established and already publicly recognised: at the end of 2017 I was selected by Sydonia Production, a professional motion picture producing company, as one of the main experts to appear in *The Sybil - Between*

Legend and Truth, a docufiction staging the mystery and fascination of the Apennine Sibyl, released one year later.

Fig. 48 - Michele Sanvico appearing in the Sydonia Production's docufiction *The Sybil - Between Legend and Truth* (released on Dec 20th 2018)

That was for the Sibyl; but still no dedicated insight I had carried out with respect to the Lake of Pilate, which I still considered as a second-rank, less-interesting tale. And yet a new occasion popped up, providing me with a reason to run this path as well.

In that same beginning of 2019, I was selected by a national TV show, *Linea bianca*, as an expert who would deliver a short interview on the Sibillini Mountain Range's legends on the top of Mount Vettore, after a flight with an helicopter right on to the mountain's cliff. So I had to briefly rehearse all the research I had just released on the Sibyl, but also the basic information concerning Pilate and his Lake, which I had never confronted with before.

Fig. 49 - The production crew of TV show *Linea Bianca* with a steadycam on the top of Mount Vettore on Jan, 15th 2019

And it was another illumination. While perusing the available literature on Pontius Pilate and his legendary tradition, I found out that the Roman prefect had been a primary figure in a multitude of medieval tales, which all focussed on his doom and ultimate destiny as the man who unrightfully sentenced Jesus Christ to death. And the location of the burial place of his cursed body had been at the center of speculations for centuries, involving a number of legendary sites and with a deviation amid the Sibillini Mountain Range as well.

This was no new advancement in the topic as many scholars have been positively working on Pontius Pilate for as much as two centuries now: but my paper *A legend for a Roman prefect: the Lakes of Pontius Pilate*, released at the mid of 2019, maybe was the first to comprehensively retrace the whole literary tradition relating to the ancient prefect, with a full analysis dedicated to the transplant of this lore in Italy, between the provinces of Umbria and Marche.

This was the second tier of my research on the Sibillini Mountain Range: I had addressed both the Sibyl and Pilate, the Cave and Lake, with their foreign origin and derivation from extraneous legendary traditions. I was now ready to run the further leg of my research journey, that would lead me to hit the target I had already set more than a year earlier: the establishment of a connection between the lore living at the Cave and Lake and the peculiar seismic behavior of the Sibillini Mountains.

Still I worked in secrecy, unveiling nothing that may suggest that my target was related to earthquake. I did not want to spoil my research vantage position with an early discovery, which would possibly allow other scholars to seize my idea and claim the ownership of the new conjectural model.

So I began to put together the two legendary tales which formed the basis of the Sibillini Mountain Range's lore, the Sibyl and Pilate, by identifying their common traits (*Sibillini Mountain Range: the legend before the legends*, 2019) and with the specific development of the insight on one of those traits, namely the otherworldly character of both legends (*Sibillini Mountain Range, a Cave and Lake to the Otherworld*, 2020). This latter paper proved to be a sort of adventurous, daring journey, as nobody had ever hunted this particular interpretative path with relation to the Sibillini Mountains and I did not know if I would succeed in the attempt; however the bounty of Otherworld-related clues I could retrieve in the two legends was so rewarding, with a plethora of references to ancient, illustrious otherworldly tales concerning subterranean sites, such as the Lake of Avernus and the Purgatory of St. Patrick, that I soon realized I was proceeding along a most promising path: a path that was leading my steps straight to my originally-selected target, i.e. earthquakes.

It was the beginning of the year 2020: now I was ready, I was fully equipped to jump the final leap, to run the ultimate leg that would bring my research on a Sibyl and a Roman prefect, through an otherworldly approach, down to the inner, most antique core of the legends of the Sibillini Mountain Range: earthquakes, the fear of earthquakes, and a possible cult of earthquakes' subterranean demons.

But that was when the coronavirus pandemics broke out. It was March 2020, and I had just started writing what was intended to be as the summa of my years-long research work, the paper *Sibillini Mountain Range, the chthonian legend*. Heavily shelled by the daily TV news - which supported an appalling narrative of social disruption and impending death - the main emergency target became to complete the paper before... passing away after getting the fatal infection!

Of course, the worst case never occurred (and here we might effectively start to quote from my other fundamental series of articles *The Coronavirus*

Papers, but this is not the right place...), so the effect of pandemics was merely a deliberate speed-up in the paper production process, yet by maintaining in the course the same level of writing quality.

Fig. 50 - The FB announcement about the release of *The chthonian legend*

Finally, there it was: on March, 25th 2020 *Sibillini Mountains, the chthonian legend* appeared on Zenodo.org, ResearchGate.net and Academia.edu, and was heralded by an enthusiastic message posted on Facebook which proudly read «Today, after a work that has lasted for more than two years, I finally completed and released the research paper "SIBILLINI MOUNTAIN RANGE, THE CHTHONIAN LEGEND". This comprehensive article is the conclusive chapter of an investigation that casts a new, possibly definitive light on the legends of the Apennine Sibyl and the Lakes of Pilate, set amid the Sibillini Mountain Range, in central Italy. It provides scientific, motivated answers, never presented before by any researcher of scholar».

And here still it is: a breakthrough research which retraces more than a hundred fifty years of puzzled investigation into the mystery of the Sibillini Mountain Range. And finds a possible final answer.

5.4 Abyssus Sibyllae: the vibrations beneath 'The chthonian legend'

The Sibillini Mountain Range and the earthquakes. A dark, frightful Cave and a potency hidden beneath the ground. A Lake encircled by ghastly peaks and vibrating sounds coming from down below.

The chthonian legend is certainly a most bewitching conjecture, which confronts with eerie legendary traditions concerning a Sibyl and a Roman prefect through a fascinating geomythological approach, in which natural sites acquire a special significance as 'hot-spots', or point of contacts towards supernatural, otherworldly regions inhabited by gods or demons, and normally inaccessible to men: «A passageway to some sort of supposed demonic presence», I wrote, «An access that was to be unlocked by means of necromantic rituals. A point of contact with a subterranean Otherworld. A 'hot spot', a crevice drilled into the mountains to establish an appalling communication with the chthonian powers beneath. A break in the continuum of our ordinary world».

So Nature 'vibrates', in a peculiar manner, in certain places and often at specific times, signalling the presence of the divine and the uncanny. And it is a sort of poetical sensitivity, enhanced by the attendance of specific literary moods, that can help human beings in the hunt for the otherworldly while living, at the same time, in a harsh, prosaic, unheeding world.

I want to conclude the present paper by retracing the origin of this peculiar poetical acuteness, which, ten years before the release of *The chthonian legend*, was fully present in my novel *The eleventh Sibyl - Abyssus Sibyllae*. The book was centered on Norcia, the Sibillini Mountain Range and the figure of the Apennine Sibyl; and earthquakes were already there, with all their potency as heralds of the chthonian powers which lurked under the mountains since time immemorial: at that time I was not aware of their potential, prominent role in the sibilline tradition, yet they were actually

laying there, as an ominous vibrating background which pulsed across all the chapters of the novel, a presage of the geomythological model still to come:

Fig. 51 - The cover of *The Eleventh Sibyl - Abyssus Sibyllae*

«An inhuman beast lived unseen under the ground, awaiting. Beneath the square and the streets and the ancient dwellings of men, the faceless being with gleaming, sightless eyes waited patiently, in a dream. Its dream, the dream of a dark subterranean potency lasted for whole lifetimes of men, looming over them as though heavy, rolling vapours announcing the coming of a storm; until, all of a sudden, the blind, faceless beast awoke, and manifested its cruel abomination across the surface of the earth».

These sentences I wrote in the second chapter of *The eleventh Sibyl*. And I concluded that chapter with words that would have fully lived their own life ten years later, taking their final shape in the research conducted within *The chthonian legend*: «I did not know what vibrated under the town, and underneath the neighbouring mountains. But I knew that something unspeakable, something unnoticed by others had echoed within my soul;

something that was buried in the abysses of time, had called and spoken to me; and finally, had brushed me with a gelid touch. And Sibyl was its name».

Thus already in 2010 the Apennine Sibyl and the earthquakes seemed to show, in my personal vision as a writer and 'poetical' observer, an inexplicable, unexplained mutual connection. That initial foreshadowing would evolve, many years later, into the full conjectural model developed within the framework of *The chthonian legend*. But everything was already there, overshadowed as it was, small and immature but ready for its full development when the right time would come.

The eerie, the uncanny, the appalling. All was already there, in the description of the high crests of the Sibillini Mountain Range, unearthly silent under the rage of the midday sun, I included in *The eleventh Sibyl*:

«And, that very moment, I was stricken with panic. The sun, high up in the sky, cast all around its ardent beams, as if they were darts being shot by a magical, gigantic bow, pointing towards the defenceless earth. That was the time of the midday fiend, when the refulgent star at its culmination exhausts and blots out the shadows of the living beings, who become the prey, according to an ancient Jewish lore, of the evil potencies dwelling in the countryside flooded with sunlight, along the secluded trails running across the fields, and in far-off, deserted places; they were eerie creatures, who would fall upon the wayfarer in the bedazzling radiance of the midday sun, sucking their blood and lives and taking away their very souls, weakened by the dull stupefaction brought about by the glowing star».

When I wrote *The eleventh Sibyl*, I was strongly influenced by the literary visions mastered by a great American author, H. P. Lovecraft. A human world immersed in a gigantic, uncaring cosmical setting, inhabited by god-like, malevolent beings, for which men are mere accidental creatures; a feeling of awe-stricken impotence before the grandest manifestations of natural powers; the fear for the unknown, hiding just beneath the surface of daily life; the incomprehension and stolidity of fellow-men, living their lives in the utter awareness of the potencies that rule their existence; a sense of imminent danger, as one gets nearer to the truth and discovers those peculiar 'hot spots' which are entryways to the subterranean reality of life. And vibrations everywhere, marking the presence of the uncanny: «the

unexplored, the unexpected», writes Lovecraft, «the thing that is hidden and the changeless thing that lurks behind superficial mutability».

Like HPL's Arkham, the small town of Norcia, in central Italy, the access point to the Sibyl's legend, is a place that «quivered and trembled underneath the visible surface of the public square: a town which had been in existence since remotely distant ages; a town which had lived, rejoiced, prayed, and endured suffering for innumerable generations of men [...]. Past the ordinary and commonplace life, beyond its visible semblance, Norcia offered itself to the sight of anyone who intended to investigate deeper in a view to catching the ripples of everyday life as well as the bigger, longer waves which utterly encompass us, so that it is hard to perceive them. They are made manifest only to those who have been taught how to conceive the vertiginous depths of inaccessible ravines, the unbroken vertical extension of ages consigned to secluded, forgotten recesses of time, and the endless sequence of unknown human lives; lives of men whose names are now lost amidst the mountain sides, the woody forests and the ploughed fields, in our present times run by nowadays machinery with bowels of rubber and iron rumbles».

It is like leaning over an abyss: not by mere chance, the original title of my novel was *Abyssus Sibyllae*.

Earthquakes, vibrations, otherworld, antique layers of forgotten history. All were keywords to both the novel and the subsequent research carried out with *The chthonian legend*.

In writing the concluding, most compelling chapters of the book, when the main character of *The Eleventh Sibyl* climbs Mount Sibyl's top to reach the entrance of the Cave - set beyond the rocky crown that encircles the summit of the mount (as it is in actual reality) and marks a sort of otherworldly region, only inhabited by the powers of deities - I wanted to render all the supernatural dimension of that eerie place, which a decade later I would envisage as a potential site for a highland shrine, in which rituals for the appeasement of earthquakes might have been performed during the Iron Age.

A first precious inspiration I found in HPL himself, with his tale *The Strange High House in the Mist*, in which he masterfully describes the

weird sense of dizziness arising from the entrance into an elevated, unearthly realm, ruled by the whiteness of cloudy fogs:

«In the morning mist comes up from the sea by the cliffs beyond Kingsport. White and feathery it comes from the deep to its brothers the clouds, full of dreams of dank pastures and caves of leviathan. [...] All around him was cloud and chaos, and he could see nothing below but the whiteness of illimitable space...».

Fig. 52 - Howard Phillips Lovecraft's *The Strange High House in the Mist*, in *Weird Tales*, Vol. XVIII, no. 3 (Indianapolis, 1931)

And this bewilderment I expressed following the words written by Lovecraft:

«The trail, hidden from view due to the glowing mist made of frosty vapours which ascended the mountain-side in drifting swirls, apparently went up only for an unreasonably short stretch, as it seemed to die away into the radiant whiteness of the fog [...] Blinded, bewildered, enshrouded in the gelid, diaphanous luminosity which shone all around, as an ethereal,

uneearthly glow, which concealed from view the airy trails running along the ridges and flanking the atrocious ravines [...] Hazy whirling shadows appeared to flock that deserted and suspended region, swept over by the weather's tumultuous rage; they rushed from one side of the mountain-top to the other, with a quick swirling motion, as though all the wicked creatures of the air, the eerie and unholy inhabitants of the upper sky had also convened at the sinister cavern of the Sibyl».

The second inspiration came from Edith Wharton's *Miss Mary Pask*, a blood-curdling tale on a visit to a dead person in a house enshrouded in total darkness:

«The darkness grew three times as thick; and the sense I had had for some time of descending a gradual slope now became that of scrambling down a precipice. [...] Night and fog were now one, and the darkness as thick as a blanket. I felt vainly about for a bell. At last my hand came in contact with a knocker and I lifted it. [...] The light went out, and I stood there - we stood there - lost to each other in the roaring coiling darkness. My heart seemed to stop beating; I had to fetch up my breath with great heaves that covered me with sweat. The door - the door - well, I knew I had been facing it when the candle went. Something white and wraithlike seemed to melt and crumple up before me in the night, and avoiding the spot where it had sunk away I stumbled around it in a wide circle, got the latch in my hand, caught my foot in a scarf or sleeve, trailing loose and invisible, and freed myself with a jerk from this last obstacle. I had the door open now...».

This same sense of blinded, darkness-driven terror I transplanted into the very vestibule of the Sibyl's Cave, as the main character makes his way into it:

«I entered [...] the sombre hollow, its hideous boundaries of rock enshrouded in darkness beyond the thin radiant beam that trickled from my faint, wavering flashlight. [...] Its farthest side was sealed by a wall of stone, on which a gate of darkness, an entryway gaping onto the eerie, lifeless bowels of the mount, gave access to the winding tunnels that descended rapidly into the core of the cliff, penetrating deeply into the mountain's concealed foundations. [...] I proceeded, the way a madman does, by crossing the ghastly entrance, between coarse walls of stone,

dripping with water, and falling seemingly back into the darkness beyond the scant glow cast by my feeble light. [...] I stepped forward, and then my flashlight quivered, and went out. The frenzied voices reached a climax, the piercing wails rose hideously in the darkness that had abruptly curdled about my frame. And then the voices fell silent at once; only an indistinct rustle still lingered in the dark, now turning into a solid black shroud; muttering whispers, murmurs chasing and querying each other in the stygian emptiness, arising from sheer gloom; a feeling of queer and restless movements; stealthy, uneasy footfalls sneaking all around, and weak, insubstantial fingers touching my arms and face».

Fig. 53 - Edith Wharton's *Ghosts* (New York, 1937), containing the tale *Miss Mary Pask*

The whiteness of supernatural fogs protecting the entryway to the Otherworld and the gloominess of the Netherworld itself, an eerie land of dead. All the sensations, the feelings, the colours, the sounds, the experience described on a conjectural basis in *The chthonian legend* paper, with its seismic demons and terrors and rituals, were already unconsciously present in *The elevent Sibyl - Abyssus Sibyllae*. Just as if people from the Iron Age had made attempts at expressing their own feelings, their own terrors to a twenty-first-century writer, first on a poetical basis and then through the suggestion of a model on what had been possibly going on for

centuries or even millennia at those secluded highland shrine, a Cave and a Lake, up there in the Apennines.

Nature as inhabited by divine beings, sometimes benign but often hostile and malicious; the possibility for men to sense their presence, at certain points set at specific geographical sites; the unknown, the eerie that are hidden behind any tree, beneath any rock; the vibration of centuries, carrying away with them the lives of generations of human beings, of which traces remain in the artifacts and cultural traditions left behind by them.

This is the wondrous setting of both *The Eleventh Sibyl* and *The chthonian legend*, assorted as they are in scope and reach, and separate by a full decade.

From earthquakes to an Otherworld concealed in a Lake and a Cave, and then to an Apennine Sibyl and Pontius Pilate, and finally to dancing fairies on the mountain-sides marked by the streaks of seismic faults: a long journey for which I set off long ago and which drove me across a marvellous novel and a series of rewarding research papers. I had the rare chance to explore an antique legendary lore that, quoting from Marcel Proust's *A la recherche du temps perdu* and his *Du côté de chez Swann*, was still living in the Apennines its subterranean life since time immemorial, like the recollection of Middle Ages amid the villagers of Combray:

«...une tradition à la fois antique et directe, ininterrompue, orale, déformée, méconnaissable et vivante...».

A legendary lore which is part of the larger, magnificent cultural heritage of Italy, which goes from the Iron Ages to the Etruscans, the Romans and then the artistic achievements of Renaissance, all of them immersed in the light of a natural setting inhabited by the divine and the magical:

«Had I never visited Italy I think I should never have understood the word picturesque. The very air of Italy is imbued with the spirit of ancient mythology».

These words, drawn from Anna Brownell Jameson's *Diary of an Ennuyée*, I put as an epigraph at the beginning of *The Eleventh Sibyl - Abyssus Sibyllae*.

And I am proud of having been part of this illustrious inheritance.

Fig. 54 - Mount Vettore, Sibillini Mountain Range

Michele Sanvico

Michele Sanvico
THE ELEVENTH SIBYL
ABYSSUS SIBYLLAE

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